

Self-Supervised Pre-Training for Texture Segmentation and Diagnosis in Dermatology

Master of Science in Engineering
VM02

presented by
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October 10, 2023

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Acknowledgements. I want to thank my advisor Prof. Dr. Marc Pouly, for the great discussions and support during the project. I also want to thank Prof. Dr. Dr. Alexander A. Navarini and the whole DBE team for letting me use the dermatology dataset and for integrating me into the team. Additionally, I want to thank Andrin Bürlü for many great exchanges and critical discussions. Lastly, I want to thank my wife, Deborah Gröger, for her patience and constant support throughout the project.

Content Warning. This work uses data from various dermatology diseases that might be disturbing to see. Please be forewarned.

Declaration of originality. I hereby declare that I have prepared the present work independently and have used nothing other than the specified aids. All text sections, citations or contents of other authors used have been explicitly marked as such.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Fabian Gröger', with a stylized flourish extending to the right.

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October 10, 2023
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Abstract

Training supervised models requires large amounts of labelled data, whose creation is often expensive and time-consuming, especially in the medical domain. The standard practice to mitigate the lack of annotated medical images is to use transfer learning and fine-tune supervised pre-trained ImageNet weights on a downstream task. While this approach achieves satisfactory performance, it still requires a large dataset to adjust the global features for a specific task. Additionally, this approach has been criticised in recent literature since the features learned using natural images might not be optimal to represent the medical domain.

This project aims to evaluate one of the most prominent approaches for obtaining domain-specific pre-trained models without the need for labelled data called self-supervised learning (SSL) for the application in dermatology. More concretely, this project compares the performance of five different SSL methods, namely ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO, and iBOT, to a supervised pre-trained ImageNet model. For the comparison, six different downstream tasks were defined, consisting of open-source and private as well as classification and segmentation tasks, namely Fitzpatrick17k, PAD-UFES-20, HAM10000, ISIC 2018 Task 1, body localisation and PPP segmentation. For pre-training the SSL methods, the university hospital of Basel has made a large collection of 250'000 dermatology images available.

Five models were trained using the pre-training dataset with different SSL methods. After pre-training, the models were compared in terms of linear, fine-tuned and k -nearest neighbour performance. The results from all three evaluations showed that pre-trained features from iBOT outperformed all the other SSL methods and, in five tasks of six tasks, also supervised ImageNet pre-training. Further, for multiple downstream tasks, the best performing pre-trained model reduces the number of parameters by a magnitude of four compared to the supervised pre-trained model.

The findings of this project indicate a clear benefit in using features learned by iBOT on dermatology datasets compared to conventional transfer learning from ImageNet classification. The project also showed that using self-supervised pre-trained models can, for some tasks, reduce the need for annotated samples. Intermediate results from this project will be published at the SDAIH workshop of the ECAI conference.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Research Questions and Expected Results	1
1.2	Report Structure	2
1.2.1	Notation	2
2	Theoretical Grounding	3
2.1	Artificial Neural Networks	3
2.1.1	Perceptron	3
2.1.2	Activation Functions	5
2.1.3	Cost Functions	7
2.1.4	Gradient Descent Algorithm	8
2.1.5	Stabilising Gradients	10
2.1.6	Transfer Learning	12
2.1.7	Regularisation	12
2.2	Convolutional Neural Networks	14
2.2.1	Convolutional Layers	14
2.2.2	Pooling Layers	16
2.2.3	Network Architectures	16
2.3	Transformers	18
2.3.1	Attention Mechanism	18
2.3.2	Vanilla Transformer	19
2.3.3	Vision Transformer	20
2.4	Exemplar-based Methods	21
2.4.1	k -Nearest Neighbour Classification	21
2.5	Self-Supervised Learning	22
2.5.1	Predictive Approaches	22
2.5.2	Generative Approaches	22
2.5.3	Contrastive Approaches	23
2.5.4	Multi-task Approaches	29
2.6	Dermatology	30
2.6.1	Dermoscopy Images	30
2.6.2	Clinical Images	30
3	Methodology	31
3.1	Dataset	31
3.1.1	Pre-training data	31
3.1.2	Downstream tasks	32
3.2	Pre-processing	34
3.2.1	Pre-training	34
3.2.2	Fine-tuning	34
3.3	Experimental Setup	36
3.3.1	Training Setup	36
3.3.2	Backbones	36
3.3.3	Baseline Models	36
3.3.4	Self-Supervised Learning Models	36
3.3.5	Fine-tuning Models	38
3.3.6	PyPi Package	39

3.4	Metrics	40
4	Results	41
4.1	Pre-training	41
4.2	Linear Evaluation	45
4.3	Fine-tuning	46
4.4	k -Nearest Neighbour	48
4.5	Self-Supervised Pre-training and Fine-tuning Tips	49
4.6	Summary of the Results	50
5	Discussion	51
5.1	Outlook	51
5.2	Conclusion	52
A	Appendix	53
A.1	Source Code	53
A.1.1	Makefile	53
A.2	Pre-training Hyperparameters	54
A.2.1	ColorMe	54
A.2.2	SimCLR	55
A.2.3	BYOL	56
A.2.4	DINO	57
A.2.5	iBOT	58
A.3	Pre-training Data Augmentation	59
A.3.1	SimCLR	59
A.3.2	BYOL	59
A.3.3	DINO	60
A.3.4	iBOT	61
A.4	Fine-tuning Hyperparameter Grid	62
A.4.1	Classification	62
A.4.2	Segmentation	62
A.5	Published Paper at the SDAIH Workshop of the ECAI Conference	62

Chapter 1

Introduction

Current artificial intelligence applications to medical imaging often rely on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) trained in a supervised way. These models have shown remarkable performance across many medical tasks due to their ability to deal with raw image data (Brinker et al., 2019). However, CNNs typically require vast amounts of annotated data to achieve the high performance and robustness required in this field. In the medical domain, annotated samples can be hard to obtain. For example, the acquisition process needs to consider strict regulations and the fact that collecting standardised images generally requires special equipment, such as a photo box. Additionally, there is a strong geographic influence on the data collection (Groh et al., 2021), for example, patients in Swiss hospitals predominantly have light skin pigmentation, and insect bites are rarely seen, while they rank among the most prevalent skin diseases in African countries.

Although a diagnosis is usually reported in patient files, one typically needs to recruit and train several dermatologists to do a tedious labelling job if more detailed information is required. During the labelling process, it is hard to get experts to agree on a common answer for several medical conditions, which is especially true for obtaining segmentation masks (Jacob et al., 2021). This explains why the most popular general-purpose image dataset, ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009), has 200 times more pictures than the biggest public dermoscopy dataset and 2000 times more than the largest public clinical image collection¹. The largest public dataset with segmentation masks in dermatology, on the other hand, only contains 1000 annotated images (Codella et al., 2018).

Data scarcity in the medical domain is often tackled by using transfer learning, which can leverage knowledge from a source task with plenty of data to perform a target task where data is limited. The most common approach to transfer learning is pre-training large models such as residual neural network (ResNet) on massive labelled image datasets such as ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009). Models pre-trained on ImageNet are widely used in the medical domain. However, this is a suboptimal approach since features extracted from natural images may not be ideal representations in some medical contexts (Matsoukas et al., 2022). Because of this reason, there has been a growing interest in using domain-specific pre-training. One approach to obtaining domain-specific pre-trained models without the need for labelled data is called SSL, a hybrid approach that combines supervised and unsupervised learning. It aims at learning semantically useful features by creating a supervised objective from a pool of unlabelled data (Shurrab and Duwairi, 2021). Recently SSL became popular in the medical domain as large volumes of unlabelled data are easier to obtain than their annotated counterparts. Several works have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach for classification (Li et al., 2021), for localisation (Sowrirajan et al., 2021), and for segmentation (Xie et al., 2020).

1.1 Research Questions and Expected Results

For this project, the university hospital of Basel has provided an unlabelled dataset of approximately 250'000 dermatology images as digital files. These images originate from public and private dataset collections from various hospitals worldwide. This project aims to examine if using self-supervised learning can come up with better parameter initialisations for transfer learning compared to supervised pre-training on ImageNet. Additionally, this project wants to investigate if using SSL can help mitigate the need for annotated samples in dermatology. By developing a domain-specific pre-training

¹<https://www.isic-archive.com/>, accessed on 20.05.2022

for dermatology, we support current research by the university hospital of Basel that aims to mitigate the need for annotated samples to detect dermatological diseases in third-world countries such as Africa. To summarise, the main aspects of the project are:

- Research and report the state-of-the-art of self-supervised pre-training methods with a particular focus on the domain of medical image analysis
- Definition and implementation of a task agnostic self-supervised pre-training pipeline for medical image analysis
- Definition of up to five downstream tasks for model comparison between supervised and self-supervised pre-training
- Model evaluation and comparison on each of the downstream task
- Out-of-distribution testing with unseen dermatological images

1.2 Report Structure

The report consists of five chapters. The first one introduces the problems present in current approaches in dermatology, the motivation, research questions and expected results. The second describes and reviews the theoretical concepts used throughout this project. The third chapter introduces the dataset used for pre-training and the downstream tasks used for evaluation and comparison. It also introduces the implemented preprocessing pipeline and models used to address the research questions. Chapter four describes the results of the conducted experiments. Finally, the last chapter discusses the results and describes further work and applications of the project.

1.2.1 Notation

Throughout this report, vectors and matrices are written in bold. The most frequently used mathematical notations are listed below.

t Discrete time step

\mathbb{R} Set of real numbers

\cdot Multiplication

\odot Element-wise multiplication

\star Convolution operation

θ Parameters of the machine learning model

\mathbf{y} Vector of the ground truth values

$\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ Vector of the model predictions

\mathcal{L} Cost or loss function

σ Sigmoid activation function

\mathbf{b} Bias vector of the model

$a_i^{(l)}$ Activation of node i of layer l

$z_i^{(l)}$ Inner activation of node i of layer l

\mathbf{h} Hidden state of a recurrent neural network

$[\mathbf{A}; \mathbf{B}]$ Concatenation of the vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B}

Chapter 2

Theoretical Grounding

This chapter introduces fundamental concepts used throughout this report. It starts with the basics of neural networks (see 2.1) and then explains how convolutional (see 2.2) and transformer-based networks (see 2.3) work in the context of computer vision. Then it discusses several self-supervised learning methods used in computer vision (see 2.5), and in the end, a short introduction to dermatology and the images found in this medical domain is given (see 2.6).

2.1 Artificial Neural Networks

This section introduces the concepts of artificial neural networks (ANNs) which are the basic building blocks for all models that follow.

2.1.1 Perceptron

Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts introduced the first neural network (NN) in 1943 in their paper McCulloch and Pitts (1943), where they proposed a computational model for a NN based on an algorithm called threshold logic. To develop the NN, they used observations about the neurophysiology of the brain. In simplified terms, the brain can be described similar to a net of neurons where each neuron has a soma and an axon. The soma denotes the corpus of the neuron and the axon, a nerve's extension for the connection with others. Synapses exist between the axon of one neuron and the soma of another. The neuron sends an impulse if its excitation exceeds a certain threshold. Later in 1958 Frank Rosenblatt extended this idea of a NN to the Perceptron formulation (Rosenblatt, 1958). It is one of many neuron representations used within neural networks but certainly one of the most foundational and popularly referenced.

A perceptron is the simplest model of a neuron, which consists of n number of inputs and only one output. It further consists of multiple weights, a bias and an activation function. The building blocks and the procedure of calculating an output are visualised in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Visualisation of a perceptron

The inputs, denoted as $x_1, x_2, x_3 \in \mathbb{R}$, are the values passed into the perceptron. The weights $\theta_{11}, \theta_{12}, \theta_{13} \in \mathbb{R}$ are values which are multiplied with the respective input. The bias $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ is a special

weight, which shifts the input to the activation function. And the activation function $f(\cdot)$ is used to introduce non-linearity into the output. Without it, the NN would only be capable of representing linear functions. With the non-linearity of the activation function, a layered NN with enough capacity can learn any function. See the universal approximation theorem for proof (Cybenko, 1989). Such non-linear activation functions will be discussed in further detail in 2.1.2. The output a_i is the result of the activation function, and it can be computed using equation 2.1. In the case of a perceptron, it is the output of the NN. The meaning of the output \hat{y} changes depending on the last activation function used to compute it. For example, it can be interpreted as the probability of belonging to the positive class (Sigmoid, 2.1.2) or a probability distribution over multiple mutual exclusive classes (Softmax, 2.1.2). The process of calculating the output of a NN is called *forward propagation*.

$$a_i = f(z_i) = f\left(b_i + \sum_{j=1}^n \theta_{ij} \cdot x_j\right) \text{ for } x_i, \theta_{ij}, b_i \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2.1)$$

Multi-Layer Perceptron

In deeper networks, the output of one layer is passed as input to the next one. Each of those layers consists of multiple perceptrons. Thus this is often called a multi-layer perceptron (MLP), illustrated in figure 2.2. The MLP shown in figure 2.2 has four layers ($L = 4$), from which the first one is called the *input layer*, and the last one is the *output layer*. The layers between the input and output layer are called *hidden layers*. Such layers are often called fully connected layers because there is a corresponding weight to each input of the next layer and thus are fully connected with the layer before and after.

Figure 2.2: Visualisation of a multilevel perceptron, where z_1^1 is one example of a single perceptron in the network

Training Process

To produce reliable results, the NN has to learn the optimal parameters $\theta_{ji}^{(l)}$ for a given problem. This procedure consists of two parts, backpropagation and optimisation. Backpropagation refers to an algorithm for computing the gradients of the loss function with respect to the parameters to see how good the current predictions are. Refer to Goodfellow et al. (2016a) for an in-depth explanation of backpropagation. The term is, however, often also used to refer to the entire learning algorithm, including optimisation. Furthermore, optimisation is the process of selecting the best element from some set of available alternatives, which in the case of a NN is the selection of the best parameters.

The first step in backpropagation is to estimate how far away the current predictions are from the desired solution, which can be computed after a forward pass using a loss function \mathcal{L} . These functions are often also called cost functions and will be discussed in further detail in section 2.1.3. Selecting the right loss function depends on the problem to be solved.

The next step in backpropagation is to calculate the influence each weight $\theta_{ji}^{(l)}$ has on the error¹. This is done by computing the gradients, given the cost function \mathcal{L} , with respect to the weights $\theta_{ji}^{(l)}$.

¹The bias b_i can also be thought of as a special kind of weight within the network whose input is always equal to 1

The gradient can be interpreted as the direction and rate of the fastest increase.

In equation 2.2 the gradients of the cost function \mathcal{L} with respect to the weights $\theta_{ji}^{(l)}$ are computed using partial derivatives. The equation computes the gradients of the weights from the last hidden layer (*hidden layer 2*, e.g. z_1^2) shown in figure 2.2 where $l = 2$. The chain rule of differentiation would be used more extensively for lower layers. The same function can further be used to compute the cost function \mathcal{L} with respect to the bias. Since the cost function is not directly related to the weights, the chain rule must be used.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta_{ji}^{(l)}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{y}_i} \times \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial z_j^{(l)}} \times \frac{\partial z_j^{(l)}}{\partial \theta_{ji}^{(l)}} \quad (2.2)$$

The last step in the learning process of a NN is optimisation. Gradient descent is one of many optimisation algorithms (see 2.1.4). It changes the weights and biases proportionally to the negated gradient of the cost function with respect to the corresponding weight or bias. The whole learning process of backpropagation and optimisation is repeated until the NN converges in a local or global minimum.

2.1.2 Activation Functions

Activation functions are used in NN to introduce a non-linearity. Without using a non-linear activation function, NNs would only be able to learn linear relationships in the data, which would result in a linear predictor. The choice of the activation function is task and model-dependent.

Heaviside Function

The most basic activation is the Heaviside function that was used in Rosenblatt's perceptron (see 2.1.1). The function is flat and not differentiable, and thus gradient descent will not work. This function is only used in special cases but is often used for illustration.

$$H(z) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Sigmoid Function

The sigmoid activation function is given by equation 2.4 and is often denoted as σ . Its derivative is given by equation 2.5. Figure 2.3 illustrates both the sigmoid function and its derivative. The function scales the values to the range of $[0, 1]$. Thus its output can have a probabilistic interpretation. It is often used as the activation of the last layer in a binary classification problem. The function itself is continuous and differentiable. The main disadvantage of the sigmoid function is that it has two saturation regions at $-\infty$ and $+\infty$, which can lead to vanishing gradients.

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\sigma'(z) = (1 - \sigma(z)) \cdot \sigma(z) \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.3: The sigmoid activation function

Softmax Function

The softmax activation function is a generalisation of the sigmoid function to multiple mutually exclusive classes and is given by equation 2.6. If there is only one class (i.e. yes or no), the sigmoid and softmax functions are equal. It is often used as the last activation function of a NN to normalise the output of a network to a probability distribution over predicted output classes. Larger input components will correspond to larger probabilities. After applying softmax, each component will be in the range of $[0, 1]$ and all components will sum up to 1, which allows its interpretation as the probability distribution function of a discrete random variable.

$$\text{softmax}(z)_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{z_k}} \quad (2.6)$$

Hyperbolic Tangent Function

The hyperbolic tangent (tanh) function, given by 2.7, produces output values in the range of $[-1, 1]$ and the function itself is centred around zero. Its derivative is given by 2.8. Figure 2.4 illustrates both the tanh function and its derivative. It is continuous and differentiable but suffers from vanishing gradients because of the two saturation regions at $-\infty$ and $+\infty$.

$$\tanh(z) = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{e^z + e^{-z}} = 2 \cdot \sigma(2z) - 1 \quad (2.7)$$

$$\tanh'(z) = 1 - \tanh^2(z) \quad (2.8)$$

Figure 2.4: The tanh activation function

Rectified Linear Unit Function

The rectified linear unit (ReLU) function, given by 2.9, is one of the most basic and most used activations. It simply replaces all negative values with zero and leaves all the others. This results in a function that is non-saturating for positive values and thus helps with vanishing gradients because its derivative, given by 2.10, is precise, and the values can not get infinitely small. Equation 2.10 shows the implemented derivative not the exact mathematical definition, since ReLU would be undefined at $x = 0$. Additionally, the function is very fast to compute. Thus making it a good starting place when searching for an optional activation function.

One downside of ReLUs are dead ReLUs, which can occur if either the learning rate is too high or there is a large negative bias. Then the activation can get stuck below 0, resulting in zero outputs and zero gradients. If many ReLUs are dead, the capacity of the network shrinks. The ReLU function is illustrated in figure 2.5.

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (2.9)$$

$$\text{ReLU}'(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Figure 2.5: The ReLU activation function

2.1.3 Cost Functions

Parameters of the model will be tuned such that the predicted values \hat{y} and actual values y are similar, i.e. near each other. This notion of distance is expressed in terms of a cost function, also called loss function. Model parameters are optimised such that this function is minimised on average or in a maximum-likelihood sense over the sample space. Different cost functions will lead to different solutions.

Mean Squared Error Cost Function

The mean squared error (MSE) cost function, given by equation 2.11, is often used for regression problems, where the goal is to predict numeric scores. It calculates the sum of squared differences of the predictions \hat{y} and the ground truth y and divides it by two times the number of samples m . The factor 2 in the denominator is commonly used to simplify the calculation of the derivatives of the cost function since it cancels out.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2 \quad (2.11)$$

Cross-Entropy

The cross-entropy cost function is suited for classification problems. Equation 2.12 shows the mathematical formulation of the function, and equation 2.13 shows the binary case.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(y, \hat{y}) = -\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} \cdot \log(\hat{y}_{ik}) \quad (2.12)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}(y, \hat{y}) = -\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i \cdot \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)) \quad (2.13)$$

Kullback-Leibler Divergence

The Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) loss function is suited for classification problems. Given two discrete distributions y and \hat{y} , KLD defines a non-symmetric distance metric of how similar the distributions are, i.e. how much \hat{y} diverges from y (Kullback, 1967). Equation 2.14 shows the formulation of the cost function.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KLD}}(y, \hat{y}) = \sum_{k=1}^K y_k \cdot \log \frac{y_k}{\hat{y}_k} \quad (2.14)$$

Dice cost function

The Dice coefficient is a widely used metric in computer vision to calculate the similarity between two images by measuring the relative overlap between the prediction and the ground truth, i.e. intersection over union (IoU). Later it has also been adapted as a loss function known as Dice Loss and is often used for segmentation tasks. Equation 2.15 shows the formulation of the cost function for K classes.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}}(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^m y_{ik} \cdot \hat{y}_{ik}}{\sum_{i=1}^m y_{ik}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m \hat{y}_{ik}^2 + \epsilon} \quad (2.15)$$

2.1.4 Gradient Descent Algorithm

The gradient descent (GD) algorithm is by far the most used technique to optimise the parameters of a NN. It was first proposed by Cauchy (1847). A prerequisite is that the cost function \mathcal{L} and all activation functions need to be differentiable and thus continuous to apply GD or need to be able to be implemented in a way that they are, such as the ReLU activation. Algorithm 1 shows how GD works. The idea behind the algorithm is that the gradient of the cost function $\nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}$ always points in the direction of the steepest ascent. Thus the negative gradient of the cost function $-\nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ points in the direction of the steepest descent. This property also gives the algorithm its name. Thus to minimise the cost function, at each step, the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ get updated by subtracting them by the gradient multiplied by the learning rate α . The learning rate α controls the influence of the slope at each step. The algorithm is repeated until convergence, i.e. the parameter updates fall below a small threshold.

GD is a local optimisation technique and thus finds local minima and not global ones. Furthermore, the local minima found at convergence depends on the initialisation of the parameters. Additionally, it is not guaranteed to converge to a solution.

The original GD algorithm has several drawbacks in the context of NN. One of such is that it has a slow convergence in flat regions. On top of that, most cost functions are non-convex. Thus, many local minima, saddle points, and flat regions exist. However, there are several adaptations to tackle the problems of GD explained below.

Algorithm 1 Gradient descent algorithm

initialize parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t$ (e.g. random initialisation)

repeat

$\mathbf{g} \leftarrow \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$	// Compute the gradient of the cost function
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \alpha \cdot \mathbf{g}$	// Step into the negative direction of the gradient

until convergence

Stochastic Gradient Descent Algorithm (SGD)

Stochastic gradient descent (SGD) is a variant of traditional GD, where the update is done by averaging over a subset of randomly selected training samples. When the subset only consists of one training example, it is called SGD, and when the subset consists of multiple examples, mini-batch GD. In the remainder of the report, SGD and mini-batch GD are used as synonyms, although they are technically not identical.

The origin can be traced back to the work of Robbins (1951), which first introduced stochastic approximation, a predecessor of SGD. Later Kiefer and Wolfowitz (1952) published their work, which is more recognisable with the machine learning variant of stochastic approximation (i.e. SGD).

Since SGD is only computed for a randomly selected subset, the minimisation will only tend in the direction of a global minimum because the direction is heavily dependent on the chosen data samples. A benefit of using a random subset is that SGD is much more efficient for large training sets and allows for escaping local minima since the randomness has a regularisation effect, which in turn helps the model converge to a solution that better generalises to unseen data from the same distribution.

Momentum Algorithm

SGD has problems in flat regions and ravines, i.e. areas where the surface curves are much steeper in one dimension than in another. In these scenarios, the parameter set found by SGD oscillates without

a clear direction or can get stuck. Thus, the progress of the optimisation stalls. Momentum is a method that was published in the work of Sutskever et al. (2013), shown in algorithm 2. It is a method that helps accelerate SGD in the relevant direction and dampens oscillations. This is done by adding a fraction β_1 of the past update vector \mathbf{m}_t to the current update vector \mathbf{m}_{t+1} . Hyperparameter β_1 controls the decay and the momentum and is by default set to 0.9.

Algorithm 2 Momentum algorithm

 initialize parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{m}_t$

repeat

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{m}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_1 \cdot \mathbf{m}_t + \alpha \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \mathbf{m}_{t+1} \end{cases}$$

 until convergence

Root Mean Square Propagation Algorithm (RMSProp)

Root mean square propagation (RMSProp) is a non-peer-reviewed, adaptive learning rate method proposed by Geoff Hinton in Lecture 6e of his Coursera Class². Hyperparameter α is crucial when using GD and needs to be carefully tuned. Thus, the idea of RMSProp is that instead of using a fixed learning rate α for all components of the gradient vector to adjust it adaptively. The learning rate should increase in the direction of slow progress (i.e. small gradient components) and decrease in the direction of fast progress (i.e. large gradient components). Algorithm 3 shows that for each component of the gradient vector $\nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$, an exponentially decaying measure with the typical scale of the components of the gradient vector \mathbf{s} is built. Then each gradient component $\nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$ gets divided by the scale \mathbf{s} . The variable ϵ is a small number for numerical stability if the denominator becomes zero. A common default value for the hyperparameter β_2 is 0.999.

Algorithm 3 RMSProp algorithm

 initialize parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{s}_t$

repeat

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{s}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_2 \cdot \mathbf{s}_t + (1 - \beta_2) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\mathbf{s}_{t+1} + \epsilon}} \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \end{cases}$$

 until convergence

Adaptive Moment Estimation Algorithm (Adam)

Adaptive moment estimation (Adam) was introduced by Kingma and Ba (2014) and combines the momentum and RMSProp algorithm. Algorithm 4 shows that in addition to storing an exponentially decaying average of past squared gradients \mathbf{s}_t like RMSProp, Adam also keeps an exponentially decaying average of past gradients \mathbf{m}_t , similar to momentum. The estimates \mathbf{m}_t and \mathbf{s}_t are estimates of the first moment (the mean) and the second moment (the uncentered variance) of the gradients, respectively, hence the name of the method. As \mathbf{m}_t and \mathbf{s}_t are initialised as vectors of 0's, the authors of Adam observe that they are biased towards zero, especially during the initial time steps and especially when the decay rates are small (i.e. β_1 and β_2 are close to 1). They counteract these biases by computing bias-corrected first and second moment estimates, namely $\tilde{\mathbf{m}}_t$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_t$. The authors propose default values of 0.9 for β_1 , 0.999 for β_2 , and 10^{-8} for ϵ .

Algorithm 4 Adam algorithm

 initialise parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{m}_t, \mathbf{s}_t$

repeat

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{m}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_1 \cdot \mathbf{m}_t + (1 - \beta_1) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) & // \text{Update biased first moment estimate} \\ \mathbf{s}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_2 \cdot \mathbf{s}_t + (1 - \beta_2) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) & // \text{Update biased second moment estimate} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{m}}_{t+1} \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{m}_{t+1}}{1 - \beta_1} & // \text{Compute bias-corrected first moment estimate} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{t+1} \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{s}_{t+1}}{1 - \beta_2} & // \text{Compute bias-corrected second moment estimate} \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \alpha \cdot \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{m}}_{t+1}}{\sqrt{\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{t+1} + \epsilon}} \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) & // \text{Update parameters} \end{cases}$$

 until convergence

²http://www.cs.toronto.edu/~tijmen/csc321/slides/lecture_slides_lec6.pdf, accessed at 01.12.2021

Adaptive Moment Estimation with Weight Decay Algorithm (AdamW)

Loshchilov and Hutter (2019) proposed adaptive moment estimation with weight decay (AdamW), an adaptation of Adam. In their paper, they showed that the way weight decay is implemented in Adam seems wrong and proposed a simple way to fix it. Libraries implemented weight decay of Adam by adding a penalty term to the loss function $\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|\boldsymbol{\theta}_t\|^2$, which is then derived for the gradients $\nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) + \lambda \boldsymbol{\theta}_t$. However, if weight decay is implemented at this point, the moving averages of the gradient \mathbf{m}_t and its square \mathbf{s}_t also keep track of the regularisation term. This led to an update rule, where the weight decay also got divided by $\sqrt{\mathbf{s}_t}$. This led to the fact that if the gradient of a certain weight is large, the corresponding value in \mathbf{s} is large too, and the weight is regularised less than weights with small gradients. This meant that L_2 regularisation did not work as intended and led to poor generalisation of Adam. The authors, therefore, suggest an improved version of Adam called AdamW where the weight decay is performed only after controlling the parameter-wise step size, as shown in the algorithm 5. When implemented this way, the weight decay or regularisation term does not end up in the moving averages and is thus only proportional to the weight itself.

Algorithm 5 AdamW algorithm

```

initialise parameters  $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{m}_t, \mathbf{s}_t$ 
repeat
   $\mathbf{m}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_1 \cdot \mathbf{m}_t + (1 - \beta_1) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$ 
   $\mathbf{s}_{t+1} \leftarrow \beta_2 \cdot \mathbf{s}_t + (1 - \beta_2) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t)$ 
   $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_{t+1} \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{m}_{t+1}}{1 - \beta_1}$ 
   $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{t+1} \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{s}_{t+1}}{1 - \beta_2}$ 
   $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \alpha \cdot \left( \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_{t+1}}{\sqrt{\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{t+1} + \epsilon}} \odot \nabla \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) + \lambda \boldsymbol{\theta}_t \right)$ 
until convergence

```

2.1.5 Stabilising Gradients

Training deep neural networks includes minimising non-convex loss functions by updating millions of parameters using their gradients as driving factors, which in many cases can lead to gradients that tend to become either very small or very large. This is called the vanishing or exploding gradient problem, which is caused by the fact that the error signal is being passed through a series of layers which can either amplify or diminish it (Murphy, 2022, p.441). This section discusses the most common approaches to alleviate these problems.

Batch Normalisation

Ioffe and Szegedy (2015) introduced batch normalisation to accelerate the training of deep neural networks and reduce the internal covariance shift. Covariance shift refers to the change in the distribution of the input values to a learning algorithm. However, later papers showed that it does not reduce the covariance shift but decouples the layer updates and thus makes them more independent. It also makes the cost surface smoother, resulting in more robust training. Normalisation typically gets applied before the activation function. However, this is still an open research question whether to apply it before or after the activation.

Algorithm 6 shows how to apply batch normalisation to each sample's activation output z_{ij} in some arbitrary layer. The same can be done for each sample's a_{ij} pre-activation. For each feature j , the mean μ_j and variance σ_j^2 get calculated. Then each sample's activation z_{ij} gets mean-centred and divided by the standard deviation, where ϵ is a small number to ensure numerical stability if the denominator becomes zero. This results in zero-centred and normalised samples \hat{z}_{ij} . To obtain the final output \tilde{z}_{ij} , \hat{z}_{ij} gets scaled by γ and shifted by β . Both parameters γ and β will be learned by backpropagation³.

In practice, batch normalisation will lead to networks that converge much faster. Furthermore, it allows for higher learning rates since the weights can be updated on a similar scale. Additionally, it reduces the sensitivity to weight initialisation and acts as a regulariser since it injects noise into the training. However, a drawback of batch normalisation is that it breaks the independence between the samples within a batch and thus is often the cause for the lack of reproducibility in experiments.

³The bias from the layer before can be removed since β of the batch normalisation replaces it

Algorithm 6 Batch normalisation

$$\mu_j \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m z_{ij}$$

$$\sigma_j^2 \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (z_{ij} - \mu_j)^2$$

$$\hat{z}_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij} - \mu_j}{\sqrt{\sigma_j^2 + \epsilon}}$$

$$\tilde{z}_{ij} \leftarrow \gamma \cdot \hat{z}_{ij} + \beta$$

Layer Normalisation

Ba et al. (2016) introduced layer normalisation to solve the problem of the introduced dependencies between samples from batch normalisation. Unlike batch normalisation, layer normalisation normalises the samples along the feature axis instead of the batch dimension. Thus the statistics are independent of other examples from the batch. Especially for recurrent neural networks (RNNs), this is a big advantage since the statistics do not have to be computed for every step. Algorithm 7 shows how to calculate the layer normalisation for each sample's activation output z_{ij} in some arbitrary layer. The same can be done for each sample's a_{ij} pre-activation. The difference to the batch normalisation algorithm is that the statistics get calculated for each example i along the feature dimension j .

Algorithm 7 Layer normalisation

$$\mu_i \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m z_{ij}$$

$$\sigma_i^2 \leftarrow \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (z_{ij} - \mu_i)^2$$

$$\hat{z}_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij} - \mu_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_i^2 + \epsilon}}$$

$$\tilde{z}_{ij} \leftarrow \gamma \cdot \hat{z}_{ij} + \beta$$

Weight Normalisation

Weight normalisation is a normalisation method for training neural networks introduced by Salimans and Kingma (2016). It is inspired by batch normalisation, but instead of normalising the mini-batches, it normalises the layers' weights. Additionally, weight normalisation is a deterministic method that does not share batch normalisation's property of adding noise to the gradients. Weight normalisation reparameterises each weight vector \mathbf{w} in terms of a parameter vector \mathbf{v} and a scalar parameter g according to equation 2.16, where $\|\mathbf{v}\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm of vector \mathbf{v} . The optimisation is then done with respect to those parameters instead. The reparametrisation has the effect of fixing the Euclidean norm of the weight vector \mathbf{w} to the scalar g (i.e. $\|\mathbf{w}\|_2 = g$) and is thus independent of the parameters \mathbf{v} .

$$\mathbf{w} = \frac{g}{\|\mathbf{v}\|_2} \mathbf{v} \tag{2.16}$$

Gradient Clipping

Neural networks with many layers often have loss functions with extremely steep regions resembling cliffs. These result from the multiplication of several large weights together. On the face of an extremely steep cliff structure, the gradients update step can move the parameters extremely far, usually jumping off the cliff structure altogether into a region where the loss function is much greater than before. Thus effectively undoing much of the work needed to get the current solution. This behaviour is shown in figure 2.6.

The basic idea of gradient clipping, introduced by Pascanu et al. (2013), is to recall that the gradient specifies not the optimal step size but only the optimal direction within an infinitesimal region. Thus, when traditional gradient descent algorithms propose making a very large step, the gradient clipping heuristic intervenes to reduce the step size to ensure optimisation performs more reasonably near sharp areas of the loss surface. The clipping can be performed in several ways. One option is to clip the parameter gradient element-wise before a parameter update. Another option is to clip the norm

Figure 2.6: Illustration of a cost function from a highly nonlinear deep neural network, containing a steep cliff. When the parameters (shown in blue) get close to such a cliff region, a gradient descent update can catapult the parameters very far, possibly losing most of the optimisation work that has been done. Figure from Pascanu et al. (2013)

$\|\mathbf{g}\|$ of the gradient \mathbf{g} before a parameter update given by equation 2.17. The norm threshold of the gradient v is a hyperparameter that needs to be tuned.

$$\text{if } \|\mathbf{g}\| > v \text{ then } \mathbf{g} \leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{g}v}{\|\mathbf{g}\|} \quad (2.17)$$

2.1.6 Transfer Learning

The origin of transfer learning can be traced back to early works of Bozinovski and Fulgosi (1976). The technique resurfaced in recent years and is currently used in various fields to achieve state of the art (SOTA) performances (Weiss et al., 2016). Transfer learning is the process of using knowledge learned from tasks for which a lot of labelled data is available in settings where only small amounts of labelled data are available. The idea is to replace the last layer in a NN with a new one and retrain it on a new dataset while reusing the first layers. This works because the first layers correspond to generic features and the last layer to specific ones. Thus, transfer learning will lead to models that converge faster without requiring large amounts of data. One disadvantage of using this technique is that if the domain to which the knowledge is transferred is too different, there will be no benefit, and it might even impair the model performance.

There are multiple strategies for performing transfer learning. The most simple one is to use a pre-trained model as a feature extractor and use these features as input to the network to train. Other strategies include removing the last layer in a pre-trained model, freezing the other layers or freezing n layers and adding a new classification head. A small learning rate needs to be used when using transfer learning because otherwise, the pre-trained features get destroyed.

2.1.7 Regularisation

Regularisation strategies are designed to reduce the test error of a machine learning algorithm, possibly at the expense of training error. This section discusses some of the most common regularisation approaches.

Dropout

Srivastava et al. (2014) introduced dropout as a computationally inexpensive regularisation technique for a broad family of NNs. At training time, every neuron, along with all its connections, has a probability p of being dropped. Dropping a neuron is implemented by masking the activation of the specific unit, i.e. multiplying its output value by zero. At test time, all neurons are present, but with weights scaled by p (i.e. θ becomes $p\theta$). The intuition behind dropout is that the model learns to be less dependent on single units. Thus, the model learns that each neuron needs to be as useful as possible on its own. Using dropout in neural networks will lead to models that generalise better.

Furthermore dropout provides an inexpensive approximation to training and evaluating a bagged ensemble of exponentially many neural networks because every dropout mask will lead to a slightly different architecture that includes and excludes certain neurons.

Label Smoothing

Instead of regularising the model directly, one can also regularise the training process itself, for example, by injecting noise into the output targets. This process is called label smoothing and was introduced by Szegedy et al. (2015). It replaces the hard 0 and 1 classification targets of k output classes with targets of $\frac{\epsilon}{k-1}$ and $1 - \epsilon$, where ϵ is a small constant. Any standard classification loss function may then be used with these soft targets.

This helps the model because maximum likelihood learning with a softmax classifier and hard targets may never converge. Such a classifier can never predict a probability of exactly 0 or 1, so it will continue to learn larger weights making more extreme predictions forever. Label smoothing has the advantage of preventing the pursuit of hard probabilities without discouraging correct classification.

Data Augmentation

The best way to make a machine learning model generalise better is to train it on more representative data. In practice, the amount of data is, however, limited. One way to get around this problem is to use data augmentation. Data augmentation is the process of artificially generating more data from existing data based on different modifications. Refer to Shorten and Khoshgoftaar (2019) for a survey on augmentation approaches for images and to Feng et al. (2021) for text data. Data augmentation not only helps to grow the dataset but also increases the diversity of the dataset. When training machine learning models, data augmentation acts as a regulariser and helps to avoid overfitting.

2.2 Convolutional Neural Networks

In the previous section, we have seen that MLPs can be used to learn functions mapping input vectors $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ to outputs $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^C$. In this section, the idea gets extended to the case where the input \mathbf{x} has a two-dimensional spatial structure, such as an image.

One straightforward idea for processing two-dimensional input vectors is to use an MLP. However, this is not optimal and would result in many issues. Recall that the core operation in an MLP at each hidden layer is computing the activations $\mathbf{z} = f(\boldsymbol{\theta}\mathbf{x})$, where x is the input to the layer, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ the weights and f is the nonlinear activation function. Thus we can think of this inner product operation as comparing the input \mathbf{x} to a learned template or pattern $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. However, this does not work well if the input is multidimensional, such as an image $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times C}$, where W is the width, H the height and C the number of input channels of the image. The problem with using an MLP for such input data is that a different sized weight matrix $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ would have to be learned for every size of the input image. Even if the input size were fixed, the number of parameters would be huge for reasonably sized images since the weight matrix would have the size of $W \times H \times C \times D$, where D is the number of hidden units. And the final problem is that a pattern that occurs in one location may not be recognised when it occurs in a different one because the weights are not shared across locations. Thus the model needs to learn translation invariance.

CNNs have been proposed by LeCun et al. (1989) to solve the above problems, where they were first used for handwritten digit recognition. After their introduction in the late 1980s, they remained unpopular until the work of Krizhevsky et al. (2012a), in which they were used to win the ImageNet challenge. Generally, CNNs can be summarised as neural networks that use the convolution operation instead of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers (Goodfellow et al., 2016b, Chapter 9). The following section describes the most common layers used within a CNN, as well as popular CNN architectures.

Figure 2.7: Visualisation of a convolutional operation. To calculate the value highlighted in blue within the feature map (right), the equation 2.18 has to be used. Thus the highlighted element can be calculated with $9 \cdot 1 + 0 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot (-1) + 2 \cdot (-2) = 4$

2.2.1 Convolutional Layers

The main part of CNNs are convolutional layers, which use the convolutional operation, as the name suggests, and have the property of preserving the spatial structure of the input by passing it through a set of filters. Convolution is a process where small weight matrices, called kernels or filters, are slid over grid-like data (e.g. an image) and multiplied with the current part of the input. More concretely, at a given position of the convolution kernel, the element-wise multiplication of each kernel cell value and the corresponding image pixel value that overlaps the kernel cell is taken and then summed up. Each filter additionally contains a bias b that is also added to the result. The convolutional operation is often denoted as \star . The equation 2.18 shows how to calculate the output \mathbf{O} at the positions i and j of the convolution of an input image $\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{h_i \times w_i}$ and a two-dimensional filter kernel $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{h_f \times w_f}$. The output of the convolutional operation $O_{i,j}$ is often called the feature map. A visualisation of the operation is illustrated in figure 2.7. In the context of CNNs, the learning algorithm will learn the appropriate values of the kernel \mathbf{F} in the appropriate place to detect arbitrary features.

$$O_{i,j} = (\mathbf{F} \star \mathbf{I})(i,j) = \sum_{m=1}^{h_f} \sum_{n=1}^{w_f} F_{m,n} \cdot I_{i+m,j+n} + b \quad (2.18)$$

We can think of two-dimensional convolution as template matching or as feature detection since the output at a point (i, j) will be large if the corresponding image patch centred on (i, j) is similar to θ . Thus if the template θ corresponds to an oriented edge, then convolving with it will cause the output heat map to “light up” in regions that contain edges that match that orientation.

Each output pixel is generated by a weighted combination of inputs based on the size of the filter. Neighbouring outputs will have similar values since their inputs overlap. This redundancy can be reduced by skipping every s 'th input, called strided convolution. Specifically, s defines the number of pixels a specific filter moves and is often called the stride size. Using strided convolution further speeds up the calculation since fewer computations must be performed.

When using convolutional layers, the filter size and stride configuration often do not match, i.e. it may not be possible to move the filter over every input pixel. For this purpose, an additional parameter called padding size p is used, which specifies the size of a zeroed frame added around the input. Equation 2.19 shows how the output dimensions $h_o \times w_o$ are calculated if a convolutional layer with filter size $h_f \times w_f$, a padding size of p and a stride of s is applied to an input of size $h_i \times w_i$. There are two main padding strategies:

Same ensures that the output after applying the convolutional layer has the same shape as the input. Thus, the padding p is selected so that conditions $h_o = (h_i + 2p - h_f) \cdot s$ and $w_o = (w_i + 2p - w_f) \cdot s$ are fulfilled.

Valid ensures that the filter is only applied to the valid parts of the input. Thus, the operation's output will not have the same shape as the input.

$$\begin{aligned} h_o &= \left\lfloor \frac{h_i - h_f + 2p}{s} \right\rfloor + 1 \\ w_o &= \left\lfloor \frac{w_i - w_f + 2p}{s} \right\rfloor + 1 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

In comparison with CNNs, traditional feed-forward networks have a matrix of parameters connecting each input unit with each output unit, which is referred to as dense or full connectivity. Figure 2.8 shows that one input, e.g. x_3 effects all outputs units when having full connectivity.

Figure 2.8: Illustration of the dense connectivity of feed-forward networks

Goodfellow et al. (2016b) describe that convolutional networks, on the other hand, have sparse connectivity since the kernel is smaller than the input. Having sparse connectivity means fewer parameters need to be stored, reducing the memory requirements and improving the layer's computational efficiency because computing the output requires fewer operations than in a network with full connectivity. Figure 2.9 highlights this sparse connectivity where only three output units are affected by the input x_3 when using a kernel size of 3, instead of all, as shown in the figure above.

Figure 2.9: Illustration of the sparse connectivity of convolutional networks

2.2.2 Pooling Layers

Convolutional layers will preserve information about the location of input features, a property known as *equivariance*. However, in some cases, it is preferred to be invariant to the location. One example is when performing image classification, where we are only interested if an object of interest is present anywhere in the image instead of knowing where exactly it is located. A simple way to achieve invariance to location is by using pooling layers.

A pooling function replaces the activations at a particular location with a summary statistic of the nearby outputs. The layer is characterised by the parameters *pooling* and *stride size*, where pooling size indicates how many pixels are considered for the summary statistic and stride size by how many pixels it moves.

There are two main types of pooling operations, max-pooling and average-pooling. As the name suggests, max-pooling computes the maximum over its incoming values, and average-pooling computes the average over its incoming values. In both cases, the output neuron has the same response no matter where the input pattern occurs within its receptive field. It is important to note that the pooling is applied to each feature channel independently. Both pooling functions are illustrated in figure 2.10. The figure shows an example of a max-pooling and an average-pooling operation with a pooling size of 2×2 and a stride size of 2.

Figure 2.10: Visualisation of the max- and average-pooling operation

2.2.3 Network Architectures

This section briefly reviews various CNNs architectures developed over the years to solve image classification tasks, which is the task of estimating the function $f : \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times K} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^C$, where K is the number of input channels and C the number of class labels. A typical design pattern is to create a CNNs by alternating convolutional layers with max-pooling layers, followed by a final linear classification layer at the end. All the networks listed below consist of a CNN backbone followed by some classification layers, thus making the same backbone architecture usable in other tasks such as segmentation or localisation.

LeNet One of the earliest CNNs, created in 1998, is known as LeNet (Lecun et al., 1998). It was designed to classify images of handwritten digits and was trained on the MNIST dataset. The model consists of several convolutional and pooling layers for feature extraction followed by a dense layer for classification.

AlexNet Although CNNs have been around for many years, it was not until the paper of Krizhevsky et al. (2012b) that mainstream computer vision researchers paid attention to them. In the AlexNet paper, the authors showed how to reduce the top 5 error rate on the ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009) challenge by around 10%, which was a significant improvement. The model is very similar to LeNet, with a few differences: it is deeper; it uses ReLU nonlinearities instead of tanh; it uses dropout for regularisation instead of weight decay; and it stacks several convolutional layers on top of each other, rather than strictly alternating between convolutional and pooling layers.

ResNet One of the most known CNN architectures today is called ResNet, which was introduced in 2015 (He et al., 2016a) and was the winner of ImageNet Visual Recognition Challenge 2015. The problem ResNet solves is the degradation problem, which has been observed when deeper networks start converging. The problem states that with the network depth increasing, accuracy gets saturated and degrades rapidly. Therefore, using deeper networks degrades the performance of the model. He et al. (2016a) tries to solve this problem using a deep residual learning framework. The core idea introduced is the so-called *identity shortcut connection* that skips one or more layers, as shown in figure 2.11a. Typical ResNet models are implemented with double- or triple-layer skips that contain non-linearities (ReLU) and batch normalisation in between, as shown in figure 2.11b. The architecture is a stack of residual blocks with appropriate stride and pooling. These resulting residual networks are easier to optimise and can gain accuracy from considerably increased depth. There are several variants of the ResNet architecture available, for example the ResNet-18 and ResNet-50, which consist of 18 or 50 stacked layers respectively.

Figure 2.11: ResNet residual block and skip connection visualisations. Figure from He et al. (2016a)

2.3 Transformers

Until now, we have seen traditional fully connected and convolutional networks, which are both applicable to images, although in the case of the fully connected network not optimal. In this section, a newer architecture is introduced, called the transformer. It was first introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017) for the application in natural language processing (NLP). Only a few years later, researchers have proposed using this architecture for non-sequential data such as images. This section will first introduce the basic building blocks of the architecture, then the vanilla transformer itself and lastly, how it can be applied to images. The first two subsections of this section will introduce the standard blocks as they were designed for NLP.

2.3.1 Attention Mechanism

The models often used in NLP before the transformer was introduced were typically autoregressive models such as RNN-based models or its variants such as long short-term memories (LSTMs) or gated recurrent units (GRUs). However, these typical autoregressive models have one major drawback, even if they are specifically designed to capture the meaning of long sequences such as LSTMs or GRUs, the entire context, i.e. history, of the sequence needs to be stored into one single vector \mathbf{h}_t . Needing to store all this information in one vector leads to the fact that long-term dependencies are hard to learn, even with specialised models. The attention mechanism was proposed to solve this problem. It is a general-purpose algorithm that can be used for any data type, such as text, image, tabular, or audio. The attention mechanism allows the network to focus on particular input portions from all hidden states of the sequence at once and thus enables the model to learn these long term dependencies much easier. An additional benefit of the attention mechanism is that it introduces some interpretability into the model since the attention score indicates which parts of the sequence history were important for the current prediction.

Given inputs $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_L)$ of size L and the hidden state \mathbf{h}_t of an RNN at time step t , the attention mechanism computes a score $e_{t,i}$ that measures how good the hidden state \mathbf{h}_t at time step t aligns with the input \mathbf{x}_i at position i , given by equation 2.20.

$$e_{t,i} = \text{score}(\mathbf{h}_t, \mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\theta}_a^\top \tanh(\boldsymbol{\theta}_b[\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{h}_t]) & \text{Additive Attention} \\ \mathbf{h}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\theta}_a \mathbf{x}_i & \text{Multiplicative Attention} \\ \frac{\mathbf{h}_t^\top \mathbf{x}_i}{\sqrt{L}} & \text{Scaled Dot-Product Attention} \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

Since the introduction of the attention mechanism, many different attention scores were proposed, such as the additive attention (Bahdanau et al., 2016), multiplicative attention (Luong et al., 2015) and scaled dot-product attention (Vaswani et al., 2017), shown in equation 2.20. Both $\boldsymbol{\theta}_a$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_b$ are learnable parameters and are jointly trained with the model. To obtain the attention weights $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ the scores are passed through a softmax function, as shown by equation 2.21.

$$\alpha_{t,i} = \frac{\exp(e_{t,i})}{\sum_{k=1}^L \exp(e_{t,k})} \quad (2.21)$$

A weighted sum of the input using the attention weights is computed to obtain the context vector \mathbf{c}_t , given by equation 2.22. This vector contains information from the previous steps and can then be used for further processing instead of the hidden state \mathbf{h}_t .

$$\mathbf{c}_t = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_{t,i} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i \quad (2.22)$$

Concerning the terminology for attention mechanisms, the vector \mathbf{x}_i in equation 2.20 is referred to as *key*, whereas in equation 2.22 as *value*. The hidden state \mathbf{h}_t is commonly called *query* vector.

2.3.2 Vanilla Transformer

The original transformer architecture, also called *vanilla transformer*, was introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017) and is an architecture that was designed to handle sequential input data without the need to process it in order and thus enables parallelisation. It achieves this by relying on the attention mechanism (see 2.3.1). This solves one of the biggest drawbacks with RNNs and its variants: since they need to process their input sequentially, they can not be parallelised.

Figure 2.12 shows a visualisation of the transformer architecture. The model consists of an encoding and decoding part. The input to the model is a sequence $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_T)$ of length T , that first gets embedded to form the input embeddings. These embeddings are then enriched with a positional encoding to add information about the position of each input in the sequence. This is achieved by capturing the distances between the words rather than the absolute position in the sequence. If no positional encoding were used, all permutations of the sequence would have the same effect. The encoder consists of a stack of N encoder modules and takes as input the sequence embeddings and outputs an abstract representation of it. Each encoder module consists of a multi-head attention layer followed by a feed-forward layer that introduces non-linear transformations. The decoder is a stack of N decoder modules, and it takes as input the output sequence up to $t - 1$ (i.e. previously generated outputs) and outputs a probability distribution for the next step in the sequence. Each decoder module consists of a masked multi-head attention layer, encoder-decoder attention and feed-forward layer. The masked multi-head attention layer ensures that the decoder can not see future predictions. The encoder-decoder attention combines the output from the encoder with the representations of the decoder.

Figure 2.12: Visualisation of the Transformer architecture. Adapted from Vaswani et al. (2017)

2.3.3 Vision Transformer

CNNs are the most common model type for processing image data because they have useful built-in inductive bias, such as locality (due to small kernels), equivariance (due to weight tying), and invariance (due to pooling) (Murphy, 2022, p.526). Surprisingly, transformers can also do well at image classification if they are trained with enough data. They need huge datasets to overcome their lack of relevant inductive bias.

Dosovitskiy et al. (2020) presented the vision transformer (ViT) model, which splits the input up into 16×16 patches, projects each patch into an embedding space and then passes this set of embeddings $\mathbf{x}_{1:T}$ to a transformer (see 2.3.2) analogous to the way word embeddings are passed to a transformer. Further the input is also prepended with a special [class] embedding, \mathbf{x}_0 . The output of the transformer is a set of encodings $\mathbf{e}_{0:T}$. The model then maps \mathbf{e}_0 to the target class label y by passing it through a simple stack of dense layers called the MLP head. The entire ViT model is then trained in the same way any other supervised classification model would be trained. Figure 2.13 shows an illustration of how the model works.

Figure 2.13: Illustration of the vision transformer (ViT) model, which treats an image as a set of input patches. The input is prepended with a special [class] embedding vector, denoted by *, in location 0. The class label for the image is derived by applying the softmax function to the final output encoding at location 0. Figure from Dosovitskiy et al. (2020).

2.4 Exemplar-based Methods

So far in this chapter we have seen NNs, CNNs and transformer networks, which are all so called parametric models, where the goal is to estimate a fixed-dimensional vector of parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ by using a variable sized dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{y}_n) : n = 1 : N\}$. After model fitting, the data is discarded and not used anymore since we now have the estimated parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

In this section, we will briefly touch on a different category of models, called nonparametric or exemplar-based models, that keep the training data after model fitting. Thus the effective number of parameters of the model can grow with $|\mathcal{D}|$.

2.4.1 k -Nearest Neighbour Classification

k -nearest neighbour (kNN) is one of the simplest nonparametric classifiers. The idea of kNN is that to classify a new input \mathbf{x} , it finds the K closest examples to \mathbf{x} in the training set, denoted as $N_K(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D})$, where N_K is a neighbourhood function of size K and \mathcal{D} the training dataset. Then it looks at the labels of the samples in the neighbourhood of \mathbf{x} to derive a distribution over the outputs for the local region around the sample. More precisely, it computes

$$p(y = c | \mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D}) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{n \in N_K(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D})} \mathbb{1}(y_n = c) \quad (2.23)$$

to return the distribution of the class labels in the neighbourhood or the majority label.

The model has two main parameters, the size of the neighbourhood K and the distance metric function $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$. For the latter, it is common to use the Mahalanobis distance

$$d_{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \sqrt{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')^T \mathbf{M} (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')} \quad (2.24)$$

where \mathbf{M} is a positive definite matrix. If $\mathbf{M} = \mathbb{1}$ the formula above reduces to the Euclidean distance. Another common distance function is the cosine distance

$$d_{\cos}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{x}'}{\sqrt{\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \sqrt{\mathbf{x}' \cdot \mathbf{x}'}} \quad (2.25)$$

where \cdot is the dot product.

2.5 Self-Supervised Learning

Given enough labelled samples, supervised learning can solve most tasks very well. However, good performance usually requires a decent amount of labelled samples, which are expensive to collect and thus hard to scale up. The amount of unlabelled data is always much more than the amount of human-curated labelled data since it is much easier to obtain.

Out of this problem, self-supervised learning (SSL) emerged. Self-supervised learning is a hybrid approach that combines supervised and unsupervised learning schemes in a “pretraining-fine-tuning” fashion. Thus self-supervised learning is an approach that aims at learning semantically useful features for a certain task by generating a supervisory signal from a pool of unlabelled data without the need for human annotation, to be used for subsequent tasks where the amount of the annotated data is limited. Self-supervised learning thus focuses on learning from real-world data instead of human-curated data such as supervised learning and is thus expected to capture more realistic features than traditional learning methods.

The self-supervised learning scheme is divided into two separate tasks: the *pretext* and *downstream task*. In the pretext task, a model is learned in a supervised fashion using the unlabelled data by creating labels using an artificial task from the data to enable the model to learn the useful features. Afterwards, the learned concepts from the pretext task are transferred as initial weights to the downstream task to accomplish its intended goal by fine-tuning. Pretext tasks play a central role in the self-supervised learning approaches and act as its main component because the downstream tasks may differ according to the needs of the task. The pretext task is often common among different downstream tasks and research fields. This property makes it helpful to categorise self-supervised learning approaches according to the nature of their pretext task. In the context of visual data (i.e. image data), we categorise SSL pretext tasks into four main categories including predictive (see 2.5.1), generative (see 2.5.2), contrastive (see 2.5.3) and multitask tasks approaches (see 2.5.4).

The concepts of self-supervised learning were first formulated in Bengio et al. (2006) where they trained deep neural networks in an unsupervised greedy layer-wise fashion by training a single-layer auto-encoder for each layer, which acted as the pre-training for the network. After training each auto-encoder for the network layers separately, the resulting weights for each layer were used as initial weights to train the whole network on a target task, which is now referred to as the fine-tuning phase.

Self-supervised learning has become a popular choice in recent years in fields where the amount of available annotated data is relatively small while the amount of unlabelled data is comparatively large. For example, high-quality human-annotated data is hard to obtain in the medical domain because it is very cost and resource-expensive. Several recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of the self-supervised approach through various medical images analysis tasks such as detection and classification (Lu et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021), detection and localisation (Sowrirajan et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2020), and segmentation tasks (Taleb et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2020). Thus self-supervised learning can act as an effective solution for the problem of annotated data scarcity as it is present in the medical domain.

2.5.1 Predictive Approaches

Predictive pretext tasks depend mainly on developing self-supervised predictive methods by learning latent features from the input data by treating the pretext task as a classification problem. One example of a predictive task is relative position prediction (Doersch et al., 2016), where the model is trained on a randomly sampled pair of patches, called central and neighbour patch. The goal is then to predict the relative position of neighbour patches relatively to the central patch. Another example is jigsaw puzzle (Noroozi and Favaro, 2017), where the network is trained to restore a set of jumbled patches (e.g. nine patches) to their original spatial arrangement.

2.5.2 Generative Approaches

Generative pretext tasks aim at learning the latent features through reconstructing the input data. One example of a generative task is a denoising auto-encoder (Vincent et al., 2008), where the main goal is to reconstruct a noise-free output from the noisy input. A noisy version of the original image is created by adding certain noise types, such as Gaussian noise. The noisy image is then passed to the auto-encoder to reconstruct the original image rather than the noisy image by minimising the reconstruction loss. Another example is image in-painting (Pathak et al., 2016), which aims at learning

rich representation by using a fill-in-the-blank strategy. In this pretext task, part of the input image is cropped or masked, and the goal of the network is to complete the masked part of the input.

2.5.3 Contrastive Approaches

Contrastive pretext tasks aim at developing robust representations from the input data by learning to differentiate between similar (positive) example pairs and dissimilar (negative) ones. More specifically, the goal is that the positive samples should stay close to each other in the latent space while negative ones should be far apart. Therefore compared to the other approaches, which learn from individual samples one at a time, these methods learn by comparing different samples. It is important to note that the definition of what qualifies as positive and negative examples depends on the approach and the implementation. In earlier works, they were often categorised by using the respective labels, and in more recent works, more extensive sampling strategies are used for this.

Contrastive Loss

The contrastive loss function built the basis of all the contrastive approaches, and it was one of the earliest training objectives used for deep metric learning in a contrastive fashion (Chopra et al., 2005). However, it is important to note that the first application of contrastive loss required to have labels, whereas the ones discussed later in this chapter do not. Given a list of input samples $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}$, each has a corresponding label $y_i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ among K classes. The goal is to learn a function $f_\theta(\cdot) : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ that encodes x_i into a latent or embedding vector such that examples from the same class have similar embeddings and samples from different classes have very different ones. Thus contrastive loss takes pairs of inputs (x_i, x_j) and minimises the embedding distance when they are from the same class but maximises the distance otherwise. Equation 2.26 shows the contrastive loss function, where ϵ is a hyperparameter, defining the lower bound distance between samples of different classes.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cont}}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \mathbb{1}[y_i = y_j] \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}_j)\|_2^2 + \mathbb{1}[y_i \neq y_j] \max(0, \epsilon - \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}_i) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}_j)\|_2)^2 \quad (2.26)$$

Triplet loss

Triplet loss was first introduced in the field of face recognition by Schroff et al. (2015) from Google, where they described a new approach to train face embeddings using online triplet mining. The introduced method helps to learn distributed embeddings by the notion of similarity and dissimilarity. The central concept of the method is to generate triplets, consisting of anchor \mathbf{x} , positive \mathbf{x}^+ and negative samples \mathbf{x}^- . And the goal is to learn a model that separates the negative pairs from the positive ones by some distance margin α ,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^+)\|_2^2 + \alpha &< \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^-)\|_2^2, \\ \forall (f_\theta(\mathbf{x}), f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^+), f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^-)) &\in \mathcal{T} \end{aligned} \quad (2.27)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2^2$ is the Euclidean distance, \mathcal{T} the set of all possible triplets in the dataset and $f_\theta(\cdot)$ a CNN that projects the input image \mathbf{x} into an embedding space \mathbb{R}^d . The triplet loss is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{trip}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^+, \mathbf{x}^-) = \max\left(0, \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^+)\|_2^2 - \|f_\theta(\mathbf{x}) - f_\theta(\mathbf{x}^-)\|_2^2 + \alpha\right). \quad (2.28)$$

Generating all possible triplets of a dataset would result in many triplets which easily satisfy the equation 2.27. These so-called easy triplets would not contribute to the training and thus result in slower convergence, as they would still be passed through the network. Additionally, there might be many hard triplets where the negative sample is much closer to the anchor than the positive sample. Processing such hard triplets early in training could lead to local minima and thus a collapsed model. Therefore the authors suggest using an online negative mining technique which ensures that triplets become increasingly more difficult as the training proceeds.

SimCLR

A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations (SimCLR), proposed by Chen et al. (2020a), is one of the most used contrastive-based self-supervised learning techniques, mostly because of its reliable performance and simple idea. As its name implies, SimCLR depends mainly on two ideas, heavy data augmentation techniques that result in correlated views for the same input and having a large batch size that includes a large set of negative samples. SimCLR learns representations for visual inputs by maximising the agreement between differently augmented views of the same sample and simultaneously maximising the disagreement between different samples via a contrastive loss in the latent space. The contrastive objective causes representations of corresponding views to attract each other, while representations of non-corresponding views repel each other. This pretext task uses so-called *instance discrimination*, where each sample is treated as its own class. The model is essentially trained to discriminate augmented views from the same sample from a large number of other samples and their augmented versions.

Figure 2.14: Overview of the SimCLR method

The SimCLR approach starts with having a set of random transformations \mathcal{T} , consisting of cropping and resizing, flipping, rotation, colour distortion and Gaussian blur. To then generate positive pairs, the method applies to each image two different augmentation strategies t and t' sampled from the set of random transformations \mathcal{T} . Vectors $(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{x}'_i)$ are then two different views of the same image. Thus for a mini-batch of N images, this strategy produces $2N$ views. Unlike the strategies above, it does not rely on negative sampling but treats the other $2(N - 1)$ samples within a mini-batch as negative samples. Therefore this method needs a relatively large batch size to achieve good results. The authors explain that having strong data augmentation is necessary to prevent the model from learning trivial agreements such as matching the colour histogram.

After the $2N$ views have been generated, they get fed into a convolutional feature encoder $f(\cdot)$, also called the backbone, to obtain a feature representation $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for each view. The authors used a ResNet followed by global average pooling as their encoder in their paper. Additionally each embedding \mathbf{e} is passed through a projection head $g(\cdot)$ to obtain the projections $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{d'}$, where $d' < d$. The projection head is an MLP consisting of one dense layer and ReLU activation. As a training objective SimCLR uses the normalized temperature-scaled cross entropy (NT-XEnt) loss (Sohn, 2016) given by

$$\ell_{i,j} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_k)/\tau)} \quad (2.29)$$

for a positive pair of examples (i, j) , where $\tau > 0$ is the temperature and $\mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \in \{0, 1\}$ evaluates to 1 if k is not equal i . The similarity function sim used in the loss function is the cosine similarity between two feature vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} , given by

$$\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{v}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|_2 \|\mathbf{v}\|_2}, \quad (2.30)$$

which computes their inner product after normalising them to the unit sphere.

The final loss is computed across all positive samples in a mini-batch. Unlike the triplet loss function, this method allows a joint comparison among more than one negative sample at each training step, resulting in faster convergence. After the model has been trained, the projection head $g(\cdot)$ is often discarded, and only the encoder $f(\cdot)$ is used. Figure 2.14 shows an illustration of the SimCLR method.

It is important to note that the authors in the paper state that SimCLR can also be trained without a projection head. However, the authors showed that without this head, there is a significant performance decrease. Additionally to the performance increase when having the projection head, it allows for more efficient computation of the similarity metric since the dimensionality of embedding \mathbf{e} is larger than the projection \mathbf{z} .

BYOL

Contrastive methods learn useful representations by bringing different views of the same example together, while examples from opposing views are moved apart. Such methods often require comparing each example with large numbers of negative samples to obtain good results. Bootstrap your own latent (BYOL) is an implicit contrastive learning approach proposed by Grill et al. (2020) that omits the need for negative samples during the training procedure. More specifically, BYOL consists of two networks as shown in figure 2.15. The first network is a trainable network called *online network* denoted with parameter θ , which consists of an encoder also called representation head $f_\theta(\cdot)$, projection head $g_\theta(\cdot)$ and prediction head $q_\theta(\cdot)$. The second network is a non-trainable and randomly initialised network called the *target network* denoted with parameters ξ , which has the same architecture as the online network except for the prediction head. The target network acts as a slow-moving average of the online network and gets updated based on an exponential moving average of the online network weights given by

$$\xi \leftarrow \tau \xi + (1 - \tau) \theta. \quad (2.31)$$

The BYOL approach starts by generating two augmented views (\tilde{x}, \tilde{x}') from the input image x by applying two different augmentation operations $(t, t') \sim \mathcal{T}$ sampled from a set of random augmentations \mathcal{T} . Both of these views are then passed through the online and target network to obtain representation (e, e') , projection (z, z') and projection p . Afterwards both p and z' are normalised via L_2 norm and accordingly fed into the MSE loss function

$$\ell(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}') = \|\bar{\mathbf{p}} - \bar{\mathbf{z}}'\|_2^2 = 2 - 2 \cdot \frac{\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{z}'}{\|\mathbf{p}\|_2 \cdot \|\mathbf{z}'\|_2} \quad (2.32)$$

or also called distance loss function. The final loss is then obtained by feeding both views once through the online and once through the target network given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{byol}} = \ell(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}') + \ell(\mathbf{p}', \mathbf{z}). \quad (2.33)$$

It is important to note that the gradients only flow back over the online network and are stopped for the target network, as indicated by the stop gradient sign `//` in figure 2.15. By designing the learning task this way, BYOL enabled learning semantic features by training an online network on an augmented view by predicting the representation of another augmented view of the same image produced by the target network. Thus both networks learn interactively from each other from the same image while omitting the need for negative samples.

Contrastive approaches could lead to collapsed encoders, i.e. if the network outputs a constant representation for all views. Usually, to prevent the network from collapsing, the standard approach is to include negative samples in the optimisation process, as SimCLR (see 2.5.3) does. However, BYOL does not use any negative sampling, and the authors have shown that the network still does not collapse. The authors hypothesised that this is caused by the usage of the momentum encoder and

Figure 2.15: Overview of the BYOL method

batch normalisation at each layer. However, this hypothesis was only partially confirmed in a later ablation study of Richemond et al. (2020). Their paper demonstrated that proper weight initialisation is more important for avoiding network collapse than batch normalisation. Batch normalisation only helps to compensate for poor initialisation.

DINO

Self-distillation with no labels (DINO) proposed by Caron et al. (2021) takes inspiration from BYOL (see 2.5.3) in the perspective of self-distillation task and is also an implicit contrastive learning approach that does not require negative sampling. The method makes use of two networks as shown in figure 2.17. The first network is a trainable network called the *student network* denoted with parameters s , which consists of an encoder also called representation head $f_s(\cdot)$, projection head $g_s(\cdot)$ and prediction head. The second network is non-trainable and called the *teacher network* denoted with parameters t , which has the same architecture as the student network with a small exception in the prediction head. The teacher network acts as a slow-moving average of the student network and gets updated based on an exponential moving average of the student network weights given by 2.31.

Until now, the method uses the same structure as BYOL except for the different names for the two networks. However there are a few differences between BYOL and DINO. The most apparent one is that in DINO the projection head is replaced with a simple softmax function to produce a probability distribution \mathbf{p} of the projection \mathbf{z} . Having probability distributions as outputs from both the student and the teacher enables DINO to use the cross-entropy loss function (see 2.1.3). Further, the teacher network also has a prediction head, but with an additional centring and sharpening of the softmax, leading to a probability distribution spiked in one dimension and low in all the others. The output of the teacher network is thus similar to a one-hot encoded vector over the output dimensions.

Another difference is that DINO uses as encoder now a ViT instead of a CNN. In their paper, the authors were able to show that using a ViT gives them an additional performance boost. ViTs were before only used with supervised learning, where the problem was that these architectures required large amounts of data to compensate for the lower inductive bias. In a self-supervised setting, there is almost unlimited data available, thus making it an optimal use-case for a ViT.

Additionally to the augmentation proposed in BYOL, Caron et al. (2021) used a multi-crop data augmentation strategy (Caron et al., 2019), where instead of only comparing one pair of augmented views per example, additional V smaller-sized images are used to increase the number of view during training. More specifically for each image n_g *global crops* and n_l *local crops* are produced, both defined by a lower and upper percentage of the image to use for cropping. Usually, more local crops are produced than global crops, and local crops have a smaller region they capture of the original image than the global crops. Typically the produced global crops are bigger than the local crops in output size. Figure 2.16 shows a visualisation of the multi-crop strategy.

The DINO approach starts by generating n_g global and n_l local crops and sampling for each of the global and local crops a data augmentation from the set of random augmentations \mathcal{T} . All local

Figure 2.16: Visualisation of the multi-crop data augmentation strategy

crops are then passed through the encoder f_s , projection head g_s and prediction head of the student to produce a probability distribution \mathbf{p}_s for all local crops. Then all the global crops are passed through the encoder f_t , projection head g_t and prediction head of the teacher network to produce a centred and sharpened probability distribution \mathbf{p}_t for all global crops. Afterwards, the probability distribution of the student and the teacher are fed into the cross-entropy loss function (see 2.1.3). Figure 2.17 gives an illustration of the procedure implemented in DINO.

Figure 2.17: Overview of the DINO method

iBOT

Image BERT pretraining with online tokenizer (iBOT) was proposed by Zhou et al. (2022) and is currently considered the state of the art in SSL across various benchmark datasets. The idea of iBOT takes inspiration from DINO and is thus very similar to it with a few additional complexities. iBOT was explicitly designed to exploit inherent properties of ViTs to learn representations capturing local and global information. Figure 2.18 illustrates the self-supervised learning method proposed by iBOT.

Similarly to DINO, iBOT uses a student network that is trained and a teacher network which is an exponential moving average of the other. The structure of both networks and also the data augmentation techniques used are the same as in DINO. iBOT also starts with generating local and global crops from a single input image and applies randomly sampled data augmentations on them. Since the backbone of the method is a ViT, the input to the network first has to be split into non-overlapping patches, as described in 2.3.3. iBOT uses this property and randomly masks some of these patches for the input to the student network, meaning that the student does not have access to all of the patches available and, thus, not to the entire image. Additionally, a special `[class]` token is prepended to the input patches. All patches are then passed to the ViT model, which projects each patch into a

Figure 2.18: Overview of the iBOT method

latent space and then passes the set of embeddings to the transformer. The output from the encoder is then an embedding vector \mathbf{e}_s for every input patch, even for the masked ones. Afterwards, all of the embeddings \mathbf{e}_s are passed through the projection head $g_s(\cdot)$ and a softmax function to produce a probability distribution \mathbf{p}_s for all patches. The same procedure is done for the teacher network, except that no masking is applied to its inputs. Thus we have the probability distribution for all of the patches from both the student \mathbf{p}_s and the teacher \mathbf{p}_t . The training objective of iBOT is the sum of two cross-entropies. The first one compares the output of the two networks when they are given different views of the same image by calculating the cross-entropy between the probability distribution of the class token from the student $\mathbf{p}_s^{[CLS]}$ and the teacher $\mathbf{p}_t^{[CLS]}$, indicated by $\mathcal{L}_{[CLS]}$ in figure 2.18. The second one compares all probability distributions of the masked patches from the student network with the non-masked ones from the teacher network when both are passed the same view, indicated by \mathcal{L}_{MIM} in figure 2.18.

2.5.4 Multi-task Approaches

With the recent development in self-supervised learning, researchers have proposed combining several pretext tasks to increase the performance and produce more valuable features. Thus multi-task approaches, as the name suggests, combine different pretext tasks by optimising both jointly during training. These methods are often designed for a specific use case, e.g. for the applications in the medical domain. This section describes one prominent multi-task approach used in the medical domain.

ColorMe

ColorMe Li et al. (2020) was specifically designed for applications in the medical domain and embeds inductive bias in its two pretext tasks. The pipeline proposed by ColorMe is illustrated in figure 2.19 and consists of an encoder, and a decoder implemented using a U-Net architecture. The first pretext task takes as input the green channel of a given input image and learns to predict the pixel values of the red and the blue channels by minimising the MSE loss on a pixel level (see 2.1.3). The second pretext task takes the same green channel image as the first one and predicts the colour distribution of the red and blue channels by minimising the Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) loss (see 2.1.3). To create a colour distribution, the authors propose to use a 5-bin colour histogram of both channels, resulting in a 1×10 distribution to predict. The colour distribution is produced by retrieving the embedding z from the encoder and passing it through an adaptive average pooling and fully connected layer. The training objective is then the weighted sum of both pretext tasks.

One main benefit of ColorMe compared to all the other SSL methods introduced in this section is that since it uses an encoder-decoder architecture, it yields pre-trained weights for both. Thus having a downstream segmentation task, the decoder does not have to be randomly initialised, which is expected to yield better performance. The authors could show that the model can learn local and global features by utilising these two tasks, which is an essential property for the application in the medical domain.

Figure 2.19: Overview of the ColorMe method

2.6 Dermatology

Dermatology is the branch of medicine dealing with the skin, a speciality with both medical and surgical aspects. A dermatologist is a specialist medical doctor who manages diseases related to skin, hair, nails, and some cosmetic problems. Some of the most common skin diseases include skin cancer, warts, fungal infections, dermatitis and psoriasis.

In dermatology, most diseases are visible to a naked eye and can thus be easily photographed, making it an optimal use case for image analysis. Two main types of images are usually considered in this field: dermoscopy pictures (see 2.6.1) taken with a dedicated device called *dermatoscope* and ordinary clinical images (see 2.6.2), which are instead collected with cameras that are not explicitly designed for dermatology. Figure 2.20 shows examples of a dermoscopy and a clinical image.

Figure 2.20: Examples of images found in dermatology

2.6.1 Dermoscopy Images

Dermoscopy or dermatoscopy refers to the examination of the skin using skin surface microscopy and is also called *epiluminescopy* and *epiluminescent microscopy*. Dermoscopy is mainly used to evaluate pigmented skin lesions. In experienced hands, these images can make it easier to diagnose melanoma. Dermoscopy requires a specialised device consisting of a high-quality magnifying lens and a powerful lighting system, called a dermatoscope, which is almost in direct contact with the skin, to examine skin structures and patterns. Since capturing dermoscopy images requires an expert and a specialised device, the resulting images are often very standardised.

The pigmentation of the lesion is then usually evaluated in terms of colour and structure. Colours found in pigmented skin lesions include black, brown, red, blue, grey, yellow and white.

2.6.2 Clinical Images

Clinical images refer to pictures of skin diseases usually taken by non-experts and feature non-standardised conditions. These images are often taken with non-specialised devices such as smartphones by either clinician but often also by the patients themselves. Clinical images play a crucial role in teledermatology, where telecommunication technologies are being used to transfer medical information over varying distances through audio, visual and data communication.

⁴Example from the HAM10000 dataset: <https://nature.com/articles/sdata2018161>, accessed on 11.02.22

⁵Example from the Fitzpatrick17k dataset: <https://github.com/mattgroh/fitzpatrick17k>, accessed on 11.02.22

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter describes the building blocks used in this project, including the datasets and models used. The models were implemented in Python 3.9 using PyTorch 1.11 (Paszke et al., 2019) and Weights and Biases 0.12 (Biewald, 2020a) was used for experimental tracking and hyperparameter optimisation.

3.1 Dataset

In this project, the data used is divided into two categories, pre-training data, and downstream tasks. The pre-training data (see 3.1.1) includes the unlabelled data used for training the SSL algorithms, which yields the pre-trained models that can be used for initialisation. The downstream tasks (see 3.1.2) are then used to measure the performance of different SSL algorithms.

3.1.1 Pre-training data

The training data includes both dermoscopy and clinical images, with the hypothesis that there are common patterns in skin pictures taken at different magnifications. We also want to learn a general representation of the dermatology domain instead of a modality-specific one. In total, we use 242'039 unlabelled images from both public and private datasets as listed below. It is important to note that no downstream data was present during the pre-training phase to ensure an unbiased evaluation. More detailed information about each dataset can be found in the original paper. The private Swiss hospital dataset includes encrypted images which are highly confidential and are thus not further examined, nor was a qualitative analysis was performed.

derm7pt (Kawahara et al., 2019) features 2'020 dermoscopy and clinical images of various skin pigmentation lesions. In addition to the diagnosis, seven pigmented lesion characteristics are provided with the aim of training computer-aided systems.

ISIC¹ is the largest public dataset available in dermatology. It comprises 107'208 dermoscopy images and features a large spectrum of pigmented skin lesions that the ISIC society has collected. These images have been used in online challenges from 2016 to 2020. The dataset features almost only low pigmented skin. Diagnosis is confirmed via biopsies and comes for most images with additional metadata such as patient age, gender and body localisation. A small subset of the images comes with a segmentation mask of the lesion. We explicitly exclude pictures overlapping with HAM10000 (Tschandl et al., 2018) and ISIC 2018 Task 1 (Codella et al., 2019) as these are used in the downstream tasks.

MED-NODE (Giotis et al., 2015) features 170 clinical images of pigmented skin lesions with the respective diagnosis. Images were collected by the Department of Dermatology of the University Medical Center Groningen, Netherlands.

SD-260 (Sun et al., 2016) features 12'583 clinical images of 260 skin conditions along with the associated metadata collected from the DermQuest website.

¹<https://www.isic-archive.com/>, accessed on 20.05.2022

PH² Database (Mendonça et al., 2013) includes 200 dermoscopy images of pigmented skin lesions. The dermoscopic images were obtained at the Dermatology Service of Hospital Pedro Hispano (Matosinhos, Portugal) under the same conditions.

Swiss hospitals is a private dataset consisting of 119’858 clinical images, reflecting the data distribution encountered in a Swiss hospital. Pictures were taken using diverse reflex cameras by a trained photographer, were anonymised, and used with approval (EKNZ-2018-01074) from an ethical committee according to Swiss regulations.

3.1.2 Downstream tasks

Six different downstream tasks were used in this project to evaluate the performance of our pre-training methods. Four of the six downstream tasks are open-source, and two of them are private tasks from the university hospital of Basel. Table 3.1 shows all tasks along with additional information. Detailed information about each downstream task is given below. Additionally, figure 3.1 shows five random samples from each open-source downstream task. To compare our pre-training methods across different dermatology specialities, we ensured that our downstream tasks feature some of the challenges present in this domain, such as different image modalities, e.g. clinical and dermoscopy images, or multi-skin and single-skin images. In addition, the tasks include diagnosis, segmentation, and localisation objective.

Source	Name	Task	Type	# images	Notes
Open-Source	PAD-UFES-20 ²	diagnosis	clinical images	2’298	smartphones
Open-Source	Fitzpatrick17k ³	diagnosis	clinical images	16’577	multi-skin
Open-Source	HAM10000 ⁴	diagnosis	dermoscopy	10’015	multi-skin
Open-Source	ISIC 2018 Task 1 ⁵	segmentation	dermoscopy	2’594	
University Basel	Body localisation	localisation	clinical images	29’801	
University Basel	PPP	segmentation	clinical images	3’624	

Table 3.1: List of the different downstream tasks.

PAD-UFES-20 (Pacheco et al., 2020), is a public benchmark dataset composed of clinical images collected from smartphone devices and a set of patient clinical data. The dataset consists of 1’373 patients, 1’641 skin lesions, and 2’298 images for six different diagnostics, three skin diseases, and three skin cancers.

Fitzpatrick17k (Groh et al., 2021), is a public benchmark dataset containing 16’577 clinical images with skin condition labels and skin type labels based on the Fitzpatrick scoring system. The images originate from two online dermatology atlases, 12’672 from DermaAmin and 3’905 from Dermatologico. The dataset contains labels with different granularity. This study used the highest level, splitting skin conditions into three categories.

HAM10000 (Tschandl et al., 2018), is a public benchmark dataset consisting of 10’015 dermatoscopic images collected from different populations. The collected cases include a representative collection of seven diagnostic categories of pigmented lesions. The images were acquired with various dermatoscope types, from all anatomic sites (excluding mucosa and nails), from a historical sample of patients presented for skin cancer screening from several different institutions. Images were collected with the approval of the Ethics Review Committee of the University of Queensland (Protocol-No. 2017001223) and the Medical University of Vienna (Protocol-No. 1804/2017).

ISIC 2018 Task 1 (Codella et al., 2019), is a public benchmark dataset consisting of 2’594 dermatoscopic images of skin lesion segmentation boundaries, i.e. binary segmentation. The lesion images were acquired with various dermatoscope types, from all anatomic sites (excluding mucosa and

²<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/zr7vgbcyr2/1>, accessed on 11.02.22

³<https://github.com/mattgroh/fitzpatrick17k>, accessed on 11.02.22

⁴<https://nature.com/articles/sdata2018161>, accessed on 11.02.22

⁵<https://challenge2018.isic-archive.com/task1/>, accessed on 11.02.22

nails), from a historical sample of patients presented for skin cancer screening from several different institutions. Every lesion image contains exactly one primary lesion. The distribution of disease states represents a modified “real world” setting whereby there are more benign lesions than malignant lesions but an over-representation of malignancies.

Figure 3.1: Samples of the four different open-source downstream tasks.

Body localisation (Amruthalingam et al., 2022b), is a private downstream task under strict regulations to localise skin patches on macro-anatomical regions of the body. The captured dataset contained 6’000 high-resolution patient pictures showing the main body regions, i.e. arms, legs, feet, hands, and trunks. These images were manually cropped into patches which only include a single anatomical region. The final dataset contained 29’801 patches of six different body regions, including an “other” category comprising randomly selected images from ImageNet. The train-validation-test split was done on a patient level to ensure no data has leaked from either set to the other.

Palmoplantar pustular psoriasis (PPP) (Amruthalingam et al., 2022a), is a private downstream task under strict regulations to detect palmoplantar pustular psoriasis (PPP) from patient photographs. The captured dataset contained 151 anonymised high-resolution pictures obtained at the University Hospital Zurich from PPP patients with active lesions. The high-resolution pictures were annotated by experts on a pixel level and split into non-overlapping patches. This resulted in a final dataset consisting of 3’624 annotated patches, annotated with four categories, i.e. skin, pustules, spots and other. The train-validation-test split was done on a patient level to ensure no data has leaked from either set to the other.

3.2 Pre-processing

The dataset needs to be pre-processed in order to be useable for machine learning models. In the following section, the necessary pre-processing steps are explained. In this project, we have two main steps that need to be performed with different data, pre-training and fine-tuning. Thus this section is divided into these categories since both require different pre-processing steps.

3.2.1 Pre-training

The full dataset, introduced in 3.1.1, is used for pre-training our SSL algorithms since we were not using any of our training data in the future. To validate our performance during training, we used one of the downstream tasks, namely the Fitzpatrick dataset, to do so. The validation set during the pre-training was used to tune the hyperparameters, select the best performing model, and visualise the embedding space during training.

The pre-training data (see 3.1.1) consists of public and private image collections. The public datasets are freely available to everyone, but the private sets are under strict regulations and are thus only available in an encrypted format on a specific machine within the network of the university hospital of Basel. All the images were encrypted using symmetric encryption in Python called Fernet⁶. Further, the images can originate from different hospitals and can thus use a different key. A custom loader was implemented to handle this speciality of the dataset that takes care of using the correct key. Furthermore, the loader was optimised to reduce the bottleneck introduced by the encryption.

Data augmentation plays a vital role in making SSL algorithms work. Thus, we implemented the same policies as described in the original paper introducing each SSL method, described in detail in appendix A.3. In addition, all images were normalised with the same configuration used in Krizhevsky et al. (2012a).

3.2.2 Fine-tuning

Each dataset should be split into a training, validation and test set according to the best practices of Ng (2017), where each split should have a similar distribution and properties. Otherwise, the training and evaluation process may suffer. Therefore, the dataset is randomly split to ensure a similar distribution. Usually, a default split of 60%/20%/20% is used. In this project, all the downstream tasks have a separate test set from the training set and thus, the dataset, i.e. the training data had to be randomly split into training and validation. Thus in this project, we used a split of 85% and 15% for training and validation and additionally used the separate test set as is.

Training set Used to train the machine learning models.

Validation set Used to tune the hyperparameters and select the best performing model.

Test set Used to evaluate the performance of the tuned model. The test set must not be used until the model and the hyperparameters have been selected. Otherwise, some test data leaks into the training or optimisation process, and the performance may be optimistically biased.

When training supervised models, too little training data leads to overfitting and thus poor generalisation. Wong et al. (2016) showed that data augmentation could be used to reduce overfitting by artificially generating additional samples from the original ones. Since all of our downstream tasks are considered small datasets, it is crucial to have a strong data augmentation policy. Thus for all the tasks, we used the following techniques:

Random Resized Crop A region of interest of specified target size is randomly cropped from the image. We used a target size of 224×224 pixels for all downstream tasks.

Random Horizontal Flip The image is randomly flipped with a probability of 0.5 in the horizontal direction.

Random Vertical Flip The image is randomly flipped with a probability of 0.5 in the vertical direction.

⁶<https://cryptography.io/en/latest/fernet/>, accessed on 30.05.22

Random Rotation The image is rotated by a randomly sampled angle from a given range $[-90, 90]$.

Random Colour Jitter The image's brightness, contrast, saturation and hue values are randomly adjusted.

Random Erasing (Zhong et al., 2017a) Randomly chooses a rectangle region of range $[0.02, 0.33]$ in the image and erases its pixels with probability of 0.5.

Figure 3.2 gives an overview of the used data augmentation techniques. The augmentation was only applied to the training set, not the validation and test set. Hence, for these two datasets, the images were only resized to the same target size of 224×224 and normalised using the same approach for the training set.

Figure 3.2: Data augmentations applied to the images in the downstream tasks

3.3 Experimental Setup

This section describes the implemented self-supervised learning (SSL) model architectures along with detailed information about their training procedures. Additionally it also includes information about the training infrastructure. Chapter 4 then presents the results from the pre-training and evaluation.

3.3.1 Training Setup

The experiments were all run on the infrastructure of the university hospital of Basel because certain images originate from private datasets, which are not allowed to leave the machines. An Nvidia DGX station is used for training, which features eight A100 GPUs, each with 40 GB of memory. In this project, we used four of the eight available GPUs. The station further features 512 GB of system memory and a CPU with 64 cores. As the experiment tracking and visualisation framework, Weights & Biases (Biewald, 2020b) is used since it also offers out-of-the-box hyperparameter optimisation tools.

A single pass through the entire dataset is referred to as one epoch. After each epoch, the model performance is measured on the validation set for pre-training and the fine-tuning. First, all SSL models were pre-trained on the pre-training dataset and evaluated on the respective validation set. Then, only after the models have converged, i.e. until the validation loss did not improve consecutively over five epochs and thus finished their training, the fine-tuning was done on the downstream tasks. However, clear convergence where the model hardly changes its behaviour was not always achieved, and often the loss kept oscillating to some small degree. In such a case, the training was also stopped and considered finished.

For the pre-training of the SSL models, after the training has finished, the last model is used as the final model instead of restoring the model with the lowest validation loss. This is because a low validation loss does not necessarily correspond to a better model since the training objective is artificially constructed. However, for the fine-tuning phase, the model from the best performing epoch is restored and considered the final model.

3.3.2 Backbones

The SSL algorithms used and evaluated in this project can be split into two groups based on the backbone architecture they work with, which can be a CNN (see 2.2) or a ViT (see 2.3.3). To ensure a fair comparison between the SSL models within the same group, we used the very same backbone when possible. To further promote the correspondence between the two groups, we selected architectures that perform similarly on ImageNet (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020). For the CNN-based models we used a ResNet-50 (see 2.2.3), and for the ViT-based ones a vanilla vision transformer tiny with patch sizes of size 16×16 (see 2.3.3). The number of trainable parameters of the respective backbones is therefore roughly 23 Mio. for a ResNet-50 and 5.4 Mio. for a ViT-tiny.

3.3.3 Baseline Models

Current approaches in the medical domain often make heavy use of transfer learning from ImageNet (Baykal et al., 2020). Since our project’s primary goal is to examine if there is a benefit of using self-supervised pre-training to achieve better and more reliable performance, our primary baseline is to evaluate our model against a pre-trained model using supervised learning on ImageNet. Thus our primary baseline model to evaluate against is a pre-trained ResNet-50 on ImageNet, where the last linear layer was removed to produce a latent vector with a dimension of 512. Unfortunately, we were unable to find the same supervised pre-trained ViT-tiny as an open-source model.

3.3.4 Self-Supervised Learning Models

This section describes the implementation details of the five self-supervised learning (SSL) algorithms implemented and evaluated in this project. Table 3.2 gives an overview of the different backbones used for each SSL method and their respective number of parameters.

ColorMe

Li et al. (2020) proposed ColorMe (see 2.5.4), a SSL algorithm specifically designed for the application in the medical domain. No official or unofficial code was found online and thus needed to be implemented

from scratch. The implementation uses the same configuration proposed in the official paper, i.e. a U-Net with a ResNet backbone for the encoder and the decoder. For predicting the colour distribution, the output from the last layer of the encoder was passed through an adaptive pooling and linear layer. Hyperparameters were tuned using the validation scores and the qualitative visualisation of the embedding space. The model was trained using SGD without any learning rate scheduler. The final hyperparameters, as well as the tested ones, are given in table A.1.

SimCLR

The proposed SSL algorithm in Chen et al. (2020b) (see 2.5.3) was implemented according to the paper with the default configurations and proposed data augmentation, which is shown in algorithm 9. The training code was translated to PyTorch from the official SimCLR GitHub repository⁷. In the paper Chen et al. (2020b) they introduced the contrastive accuracy score, which measures the accuracy of the instance discrimination task during training. This score indicates if the model can successfully distinguish between positive and negative examples in each batch. The model’s hyperparameters were tuned using this metric, the validation scores, and the embedding space’s qualitative visualisation. The model was trained using Adam without any learning rate scheduler. The final hyperparameters, as well as the tested ones, are given in table A.2.

BYOL

The BYOL learning algorithm introduced by Grill et al. (2020) (see 2.5.3) was proposed for learning semantic image features by overcoming the requirement for negative samples, for example, needed by SimCLR. Requiring large amounts of negative examples also requires considerable computational resources, and thus BYOL should perform well even with smaller batch sizes. The training code from the official GitHub repository⁸ was adapted to the needs of this project. The exact configuration and data augmentation was used as in the original paper, shown in algorithm 10. The model’s hyperparameters were tuned using the validation scores and the qualitative visualisation of the embedding space. The model was trained using Adam without any learning rate scheduler. The final hyperparameters, as well as the tested ones, are given in table A.3.

DINO

The SSL algorithm proposed by Caron et al. (2021) called DINO (see 2.5.3) aimed at improving the existing idea of BYOL by replacing the prediction head and thus also the loss function. Further, they also showed that replacing the CNN backbone with a ViT can yield a significant performance improvement. DINO was implemented by adapting the code from the official GitHub repository⁹. In their paper Caron et al. (2021) they introduced the student-teacher accuracy, which measures the agreement between the two networks during training. The model’s hyperparameters were tuned using this metric, the validation scores, and the embedding space’s qualitative visualisation. The model was trained using AdamW and with a cosine learning rate scheduler, as the paper proposes. The final hyperparameters, as well as the tested ones, are given in table A.4.

iBOT

Zhou et al. (2022) proposed the SSL algorithms called iBOT (see 2.5.3) which builds upon the idea of DINO and introduces two objectives, one for learning local and one for learning global features. This enabled the learning method to achieve the current state of the art in SSL on various benchmark datasets. iBOT was implemented by adapting the code from the official GitHub repository¹⁰. The model’s hyperparameters were tuned using the student-teacher accuracy, the validation scores, and the embedding space’s qualitative visualisation. The model was trained using AdamW and with a cosine learning rate scheduler, as the paper proposes. The final hyperparameters, as well as the tested ones, are given in table A.5.

⁷<https://github.com/google-research/simclr>, accessed on 31.05.22

⁸<https://github.com/deepmind/deepmind-research/tree/master/byol>, accessed on 31.05.22

⁹<https://github.com/facebookresearch/dino>, accessed on 31.05.22

¹⁰<https://github.com/bytedance/ibot>, accessed on 31.05.22

Algorithm	Backbone	# Params
ColorMe	ResNet-50	23 Mio.
SimCLR	ResNet-50	23 Mio.
BYOL	ResNet-50	23 Mio.
DINO	ViT-tiny 16×16	5.4 Mio.
iBOT	ViT-tiny 16×16	5.4 Mio.

Table 3.2: List of backbones used with the different self-supervised learning methods along with the respective total number of parameters.

3.3.5 Fine-tuning Models

After pre-training the models using self-supervised learning the encoder part of the models is used in a supervised fine-tuning fashion to evaluate the performance on multiple downstream tasks. Thus this section describes how the pre-trained encoders are used for fine-tuning both classification (see 3.3.5) and segmentation tasks (see 3.3.5). The pre-trained encoders have two different architectures, either a CNN or ViT based. The resulting model is the same when fine-tuning the backbones on a classification task. However, for semantic segmentation, there is a difference in the decoder part.

Classification Tasks

For fine-tuning the classification tasks, the pre-trained encoder is used as a feature extractor which produces embeddings for a given input. These embeddings are then passed through an additional randomly initialised classification head to predict the class label. The classification head is implemented according to algorithm 8. Both encoders with a CNN and ViT backbone used the same head.

Algorithm 8 Classification head, given the pre-trained encoder (`enc`) and image (`img`).

```

emb = enc(img)           // Feature extraction using the pre-trained encoder
emb = flatten(emb)      // Flatten the embedding
x = dropout(emb)        // probability  $p$  as dropout rate
x = batch_norm(x)      // Batch normalisation
out = out_proj(x)      //  $C$  units and sigmoid activation

```

Semantic Segmentation Tasks

In semantic segmentation, the goal is to predict a class label for each pixel. A common way to solve semantic segmentation is to use an encoder-decoder architecture. Typically the encoder maps the input into a small two-dimensional bottleneck which captures high-level properties of the input at a coarse spatial resolution. The decoder then maps the small two-dimensional bottleneck to a full-sized output image. Often since the bottleneck loses information, skip connections are added from input layers to output layers.

Figure 3.3: Illustration of the U-Net model. Figure from Ronneberger et al. (2015).

For the pre-trained CNN backbones we used a U-Net architecture (Ronneberger et al., 2015), which consists of a contracting path and an expansive path. Figure 3.3 illustrates the U-Net architecture. In our case, the contracting path is the pre-trained encoder, e.g. ResNet-50, and the expansive path is a randomly initialised decoder, except for ColorMe, which also provided initialisation for the decoder. Every step of the decoder path consists of an upsampling of the feature map followed by a 2×2 up-convolution (Murphy, 2022, p.481) that halves the number of feature channels, a concatenation with the correspondingly cropped feature map from the encoder path, and two 3×3 convolutions, each followed by a ReLU. The cropping is necessary due to the loss of border pixels in every convolution. A 1×1 convolution at the final layer is used to map each feature vector to the desired number of classes.

Figure 3.4: Illustration of the TransUNet model. Figure from Chen et al. (2021).

For the pre-trained ViT backbones we took inspiration from a variant of the TransUNet architecture (Chen et al., 2021). Figure 3.4 illustrates the TransUNet architecture. TransUNet was introduced to combine a transformer and U-Net architecture for semantic segmentation in the medical domain. In this project, we implemented a decoder that takes inspiration from TransUNet but works without the additional CNN part. Thus, we first split the input image into non-overlapping patches and use the pre-trained ViT as an encoder to embed all patches. The embeddings of all patches are extracted and passed through the decoder part of the architecture. The decoder consists of four blocks, each consisting of an up-sampling followed by two convolutional layers with ReLU activations. The final layer is a segmentation head consisting of a convolutional layer to produce the desired number of classes.

3.3.6 PyPi Package

During the project, a PyPi package¹¹ was developed to make all the self-supervised pre-trained models available. Further, the package should make it easy to use and fine-tune the pre-trained models for classification and segmentation. The package can be installed using pip via:

```
pip install self_supervised_dermatology
```

Afterwards, the package can be imported and used to obtain either the pre-trained backbones or a full segmentation model.

```
from self_supervised_dermatology import Embedder, Segmenter
```

```
# load a pre-trained backbone
model = Embedder.load_pretrained('byol')
```

```
# load a segmentation model
model = Segmenter.load_pretrained('ibot', n_classes=5)
```

¹¹<https://pypi.org/project/self-supervised-dermatology/>, accessed on 10.06.22

3.4 Metrics

Meaningful metrics need to be used to evaluate and compare the performance of machine learning models. In supervised machine learning, most metrics focus on how well the model predicts the actual value from the input. Since most of the datasets in this project are unbalanced, one must focus on metrics working with such datasets. Metrics such as accuracy are thus not suited.

This project uses the standard metrics for classification tasks such as accuracy (see 3.1), recall (see 3.2), precision (see 3.3) and F_1 -score (see 3.4). For the segmentation tasks standard metrics such as precision (see 3.3), recall (see 3.2), F_1 score (see 3.4) and intersection over union (IoU) score, also called Jaccard index (see 3.5) are reported.

All metrics are reported as macro-averaged scores overall classes, if not otherwise stated, and are reported for the respective datasets. The main evaluation metric for classification is the macro-averaged F_1 and for segmentation is the macro-averaged IoU score.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{N} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$F_1 \text{ Score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\text{IoU Score} = \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall} - \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}} \quad (3.5)$$

where:

- N = number of samples in the dataset
- TP = correctly predicted a positive case
- TN = correctly predicted a negative case
- FP = wrongly predicted positive case
- FN = wrongly predicted negative case

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the results of the trained SSL methods and compares them with each other based on their performance measured on various open-source and private downstream tasks (see 3.1.2). The performance is measured in four different ways, qualitative (see 4.1) and linear evaluation (see 4.2), fine-tuned (see 4.3) and kNN performance (see 4.4).

In this project, the methods listed below were evaluated. Furthermore, we used the same backbone when possible to ensure a fair comparison between the SSL models within the same architecture family. To further promote the correspondence between the two groups, we selected architectures that perform similarly on ImageNet (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020).

ImageNet The baseline used throughout this project is a ResNet-50 pre-trained on ImageNet in a supervised fashion (see 3.3.3).

- Ⓐ **ColorMe** The ColorMe method (see 2.5.4) uses two joint objectives to learn both global and local features. The model evaluated in this project uses a ResNet-50 backbone.
- Ⓑ **SimCLR** The SimCLR method (see 2.5.3) that uses positive and negative samples to generate useful features. Compared with all the other methods used in this project, SimCLR is the only one requiring negative samples. The model evaluated in this project uses a ResNet-50 backbone.
- Ⓒ **BYOL** The BYOL method (see 2.5.3) that uses two networks to generate the supervised objective to solve. The model evaluated in this project uses a ResNet-50 backbone.
- Ⓓ **DINO** The DINO method (see 2.5.3) that works similarly as Ⓒ except for a reworked loss function and using a ViT as backbone. The model evaluated in this project uses a vanilla ViT-tiny with 16×16 patches as backbone.
- Ⓔ **iBOT** The iBOT method (see 2.5.3) which is currently considered the SOTA of SSL. Similarly to Ⓐ this method uses two objectives to learn both global and local features during the pre-training. The model evaluated in this project uses a vanilla ViT-tiny with 16×16 patches as backbone.

4.1 Pre-training

All evaluated methods were pre-trained on the dataset introduced in 3.1.1 which features around 250'000 images from both public and private collections and includes dermoscopy and clinical images. All models were trained until convergence, i.e. until the validation scores did not improve for five consecutive epochs. The used hyperparameters were the same as the ones in their original paper but were adapted if the default parameters did not result in a model that converged. A full scan of hyperparameter space is not performed as this exceeds this project's scope and our available computational resources.

After pre-training, the resulting models were first evaluated in a qualitative analysis using the backbone as an encoder and embedding the training set of the downstream diagnosis tasks, namely Fitzpatrick17k, PAD-UFES-20 and HAM10000. This evaluation should give a broad overview of the differences in performance of the different SSL methods and evaluate if there are major flaws in the pre-trained features. It is important to note that none of the images used for evaluation, i.e. the downstream

datasets, were present during pre-training. Thus, the model has never seen any of the downstream images, and they can be considered out-of-distribution samples. The multi-dimensional embedding space was projected onto a two-dimension space using the t-SNE algorithm, a dimensionality reduction algorithm that aims to reduce the dimensions while preserving the same distances as in the high-dimensional space (van der Maaten and Hinton, 2008). Figure 4.1 shows the visualisations of the two-dimensional embedding space from the HAM10000 dataset for each SSL method. The figures show that models (B), (D) and (E) made a distinction in the embedding space between certain types of images. In comparison, (A) and (C) do not have such a clear distinction. Further, by visual examination, the embedding space of the ImageNet baseline model shows similarities with those from (A). Additionally, the results from (B), (D), and (E) seem to have achieved a more reasonable separation than the baseline. However, the figures show that all models show some separation between the different classes, indicating that the pre-training has yielded features useful for coarse separation.

Figure 4.1: Two-dimensional visualisation of the HAM10000 embedding space for all SSL methods using t-SNE, where the colours indicate the labels.

The Fitzpatrick17k dataset was further used to examine if the embedding space includes information about the respective skin type. For this evaluation, similar to above, the pre-trained backbone was used as an encoder to embed the images in the training set. However, for this evaluation, the colour of each representation does not indicate the respective label but the Fitzpatrick skin type. T-SNE was used to visualise the multi-dimensional embedding space in two dimensions. Figure 4.2 shows the embedding space for all five SSL methods and the ImageNet baseline. The intuition behind the figures is that if there are coarse clusters of the same or similar colour, it is more likely that the embedding space includes information about the skin type. If this is the case, using such a model to plot the nearest neighbours from a given anchor image would yield pictures with the same or similar skin type.

The figures hint that model (A), (D) and (E) as well as the baseline, are likely to encode information about the skin colour in their latent space. However, the figure from method (B) does not indicate such a clear picture as with the other three and thus does not necessarily include such information. The visualisation of method (C) shows no clear clusters nor coarse groups of the same colours, suggesting that (C) does not encode skin type information.

This evaluation aims to examine if the models are encoding the skin colour or if they are invariant to it. Encoding information about the skin type is not bad or good. However, models invariant to this property can be assumed to generalise better to the same skin condition on various skin types since they mainly focus on the features of the condition irrespective of the skin colour.

Figure 4.2: Two-dimensional visualisation of the Fitzpatrick17k embedding space for all SSL methods using t-SNE, where the colours indicate the Fitzpatrick score.

The last experiment of the qualitative evaluation is done by examining the nearest neighbours of all models when applied to an unseen dataset. We will again use the Fitzpatrick17k dataset for this evaluation since it provides the most variability in skin conditions, types, and image views. For this evaluation, the backbone of the pre-trained models was first used as an encoder to embed the Fitzpatrick training dataset to obtain the embeddings. Afterwards, two anchor images from the validation set of the dataset were embedded and using the nearest neighbour algorithm, based on cosine similarity, the most similar four images from the training set were retrieved. Figure 4.3 shows the results of this evaluation for all five SSL methods.

The qualitative results from the nearest neighbour evaluation show some interesting findings. First, we can see that our observation from the evaluation before regarding the inclusion of the skin type might be correct. In the evaluation above, we saw that method (C) did not produce an embedding space where there were clusters from the same skin type. From this evaluation, we can now see the

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS

Figure 4.3: Nearest neighbours of the different SSL methods from the Fitzpatrick17k dataset.

influence of such an embedding space. For the first anchor image and the neighbours of method (C), we see that neighbours have more variability in the skin colour compared to the neighbours from the other methods. Further, for the second anchor image, which features a mouth of a strong pigmented person, two of the four neighbours are mouths from weakly pigmented persons, indicating that this model has learned to be invariant to the skin colour. The nearest neighbours of the baseline method show that even though such a model was trained on natural images, it can produce reasonable neighbours.

4.2 Linear Evaluation

The pre-trained features were probed by the ability to generalise to the three open-source downstream diagnosis tasks to quantitatively compare the SSL methods. For this evaluation, a single linear layer was added to the frozen pre-trained embeddings without any dropout or batch normalisation, which will indicate how linearly separable the high-dimensional embedding space is regarding each downstream task. In this evaluation, only the diagnosis tasks were examined since the segmentation tasks would require an upsampling of the embedding or downsampling of the mask, which would yield an unfair comparison since this is dependent on the dimension of the embedding. Moreover, since the CNN and ViT backbones have different dimensions, this would result in an unfair comparison.

All models in this experiment were trained for 200 epochs using the SGD optimiser and a batch size of 64. For every linear evaluation of each downstream task, the optimal learning rate was found by performing the same hyperparameter search on the validation set over a grid of five possible values and choosing the one which resulted in the highest scores. The final performance of the models was then reported on the hidden test set.

Table 4.1 shows the results of the linear evaluation for all SSL methods along with the ImageNet and random stratified sampling baseline. All models show better results compared to the random stratified sampling baseline. However, the results show that the performance of (A), (B), and (C) are worse than the performance achieved by using ImageNet features on all three downstream tasks. This indicates that models with a CNN backbone do not profit from domain-specific pre-training in our setting and are better off using general features such as the ones from ImageNet. A possible explanation is that such models have a strong inductive bias and benefit more from initialisation using general pre-trained weights. Matsoukas et al. (2022) has examined the benefits of using general features compared to domain-specific ones in detail and found the statement from above to hold. ResNets have much more inductive bias than, for example, the ViTs and thus Matsoukas et al. (2022) showed that models with stronger inductive bias profit much more from having general pre-trained features than the ones without as much inductive bias. A likely reason for this is that ViTs, need already a good starting point to perform well, but ResNets, on the other hand, can start with general weights and converge to solid solutions.

Features from a ViT backbone yield less uniform patterns in comparison with ImageNet. Method (D) is only able to outperform the general features in one of three tasks and only by 3%. On the other hand, the results clearly show that method (E) performs well across all tasks and yields an improvement over ImageNet initialisation by 2%, 9.5%, and 17.9%, respectively.

Type	Method	Test F1 Score		
		Fitzpatrick17k	PAD-UFES-20	HAM10000
Baselines	Stratified sampling	33.4 %	18.0 %	14.0 %
	ImageNet	51.0 %	49.7 %	54.1 %
SSL pre-training	(A) ColorMe	44.8 %	42.2 %	47.0 %
	(B) SimCLR	37.0 %	32.7 %	28.2 %
	(C) BYOL	48.1 %	34.4 %	44.4 %
	(D) DINO	46.7 %	44.2 %	57.2 %
	(E) iBOT	53.0 %	58.2 %	72.0 %

Table 4.1: Macro-averaged F1 scores of various models and a baseline on the hold-out test set of the three open-source dermatology diagnosis downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the frozen backbone to evaluate linear performance of the initialisation strategies.

The results from the linear evaluation show that the ImageNet baseline is surprisingly competitive and hard to beat, especially when noting that this model has never seen images from the dermatology domain. Out of the five SSL methods, only one was able to outperform the baseline in this experiment. This evaluation suggests that there is not any benefit to using a domain-specific pre-training for models using a CNN backbone. From these results, we can conclude that the best SSL method is (E), which was the only one able to beat the baseline. Further, method (A) is considered the best out of the models using a CNN backbone since on average it outperformed (B) and (C).

4.3 Fine-tuning

As a second evaluation to probe the generalisation of the SSL features, a linear layer was added to the trainable embeddings for classification (see 3.3.5), and a decoder was added to the trainable encoder (see 3.3.5) for segmentation. Compared to the evaluation above in this experiment, the backbone is trainable and can now be adapted for the respective tasks. Furthermore, this evaluation is performed on all downstream tasks, i.e. open-source and private, as well as classification and segmentation tasks. The results of this evaluation should indicate the performance that can be achieved when enabling the model to learn task-specific features. The results in this experiment are not considered the best scores that could be achieved with the respective backbones since more extensive hyperparameter tuning would need to be performed. Thus the results should only give a broad overview of the fine-tuned performance. In this evaluation, only the best model from both backbone categories, i.e. (A), and (E) were evaluated due to computational limitations. Additionally, we also trained and reported the performance of the ImageNet baseline, which has shown to be a strong baseline in evaluation 4.2. Namely, this experiment examines the fine-tuned performance on the Fitzpatrick17k, PAD-UFES-20, HAM10000, ISIC 2018 Task 1, body localisation and PPP dataset (see 3.1.2).

A hyperparameter grid search was performed on the validation set over different optimisers, batch sizes, and learning rates for every task and pre-training method. Detailed information about the hyperparameter grid can be found in section A.4 of the appendix. For every model and downstream task, 20 model configurations were trained using the Bayesian hyperparameter search implemented by Weights & Biases (Biewald, 2020a) to ensure a fair comparison. The scores were then reported for the best model configuration on the hidden test set of each downstream task.

Pre-training	Test F1 Score			Test mIoU Score
	Fitzpatrick17k	PAD-UFES-20	HAM10000	ISIC 2018 Task 1
ImageNet	72.1 %	61.5 %	79.0 %	80.4 %
(A) ColorMe	71.0 %	61.7 %	73.1 %	76.6 %
(E) iBOT	73.9 %	64.1 %	82.0 %	81.0 %

Table 4.2: Macro-averaged F1 and mIoU scores of two self-supervised models and a baseline reported on the hold-out test set of the four open-source downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the trainable backbone to evaluate the fine-tuned performance of the initialisation strategies.

The results for the four open-source downstream tasks from this evaluation are summarised in table 4.2. Similar to the results from the linear evaluation (see section 4.2), we observe that using (E) as initialisation yields the best performance for all open-source downstream tasks. Furthermore, we notice that the gap between methods (A) and (E) is smaller than using linear evaluation, indicating that with enough training data and trainable parameters, similar features can be learned by both the CNN and ViT backbone. Comparing the performance of the linear and fine-tuned evaluation, we can also see that the improvement for (E) on PAD-UFES-20 and HAM10000 is noticeably smaller with respect to other methods. This suggests that the inherent structure of the dataset labels was already learned in the pre-training phase, and only minor adaptations to the existing features could be done. The results show that method (A) was able to outperform by 0.2% the ImageNet baseline on the PAD-UFES-20 downstream task, which is surprising since, in the linear evaluation, their performance was not similar. One explanation for this behaviour might be that although the initial embeddings are not as easily separable as the baseline ones, they yield initial weights that are more optimal for converging to a better solution. For the downstream segmentation task, namely ISIC 2018 Task 1, we can observe that method (E) is also able to outperform the other two methods. The results from the segmentation task further show that (A) is performing significantly worse than the other two models, which is a surprising fact since method (A) is the only one that yields initialisation for both the encoder and the decoder part of the segmentation model. One possible explanation for this might be that although (A) provides initialisation for both the encoder and decoder part, it only operates on the single green channel and thus does not have the same information available as the other two. Further, this would indicate that operating on only the green channel is enough for some of the diagnosis tasks, whereas for others, this is not enough, and thus the performance is degraded.

Pre-training	Test F1 Score Body localisation	Test mIoU Score PPP
ImageNet	77.0 % ¹	61.7 % ²
Ⓐ ColorMe	74.3 %	61.1 %
Ⓔ iBOT	77.8 %	60.3 %

Table 4.3: Macro-averaged F1 and mIoU scores of two self-supervised models and a baseline reported on the hold-out test set of the two private downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the trainable backbone to evaluate the fine-tuned performance of the initialisation strategies.

Table 4.3 shows the results of the pre-training methods Ⓐ and Ⓔ for the two private downstream tasks from the university hospital of Basel. For this evaluation, the baseline model is again a supervised pre-trained ImageNet model. However, different from the evaluation above, the baseline model uses the same architecture that achieved the highest performance in the published work by the university hospital for the respective tasks (Amruthalingam et al., 2022b,a). Thus for body localisation, the baseline model uses an EfficientNet-B2 (Tan and Le, 2019) backbone, which has roughly 9 million parameters, and PPP, a ResNet-50 (He et al., 2016b) backbone. The score reported in table 4.3 is the macro-averaged F1 score for the classification and the mIoU score for the segmentation task. The results from this evaluation should give an overview of the performance improvement that can be achieved when using domain-specific pre-training.

The results for the two private downstream tasks show that for body localisation method Ⓔ is able to outperform the baseline model by 0.8% using only half as many parameters and much less inductive bias. However, method Ⓐ is much worse than the other two methods, although it has the most parameters. This is likely caused by the fact that Ⓐ is only operating on the green channel, whereas the others use all of them. For the PPP segmentation task, both of our pre-trained models could not outperform the baseline. However, the results achieved by Ⓐ are still impressive since this method only uses the green channel and only has a 0.6% difference from the baseline method. The results for method Ⓔ are much worse than the other two, which is surprising since, on the open-source segmentation task, it was able to outperform the baseline. One explanation for the difference in segmentation performance might be caused by the lack of precise spatial information in the segmentation architecture of Ⓔ. An indication of this is that the ISIC task requires only coarse spatial information because of the nature of the dataset, i.e. all images include one lesion almost at the centre of the image, whereas PPP requires precise spatial information. The current decoder of the ViT does not use any form of skip connections and purely uses the information available at the bottleneck. Skip connections in the U-Net architecture were introduced to tackle this problem since a similar problem was also observed in CNN segmentation architectures. Thus the performance difference between the ISIC and PPP task might be caused by the lack of spatial information in the ViT decoder. Therefore, more recent ViT segmentation architectures with skip connections should be implemented and evaluated to examine if this might be the case.

¹EfficientNet-B2 pre-trained on ImageNet

²ResNet-50 pre-trained on ImageNet

4.4 k -Nearest Neighbour

The third and final evaluation of our SSL pre-training methods is to use a k -nearest neighbour classifier (see 2.4.1) to measure the performance of our embedding spaces in a low-data regime. The results from this evaluation are obtained by using a fixed amount of random samples from each class of the downstream tasks as the training set to initialise the kNN classifier and reporting the performance on the hidden test set. This experiment should give an overview of the performance of the pre-trained models when they only have limited training samples available. The reason for using a kNN classifier was that both of the evaluations above were sensitive to the chosen hyperparameters, and we observed a large variance in performance between runs when varying the parameters. Further, the kNN classifier is likewise one of the most straightforward few-shot learning principles and thus will also give an overview of our pre-training methods in such a setting. The nearest neighbour classifier matches the extracted embedding of an image to the k nearest stored embeddings that vote for the label. In this experiment, we evaluated the standard baseline model, i.e. supervised ImageNet pre-training and methods (A) and (E). To compare the performance of this evaluation and the linear and fine-tuned performance, we are using the open-source diagnosis downstream tasks, namely Fitzpatrick17k, PAD-UFES-20 and HAM10000. Figure 4.4 shows the results for all three pre-training strategies.

Figure 4.4: Results of a kNN classifier on frozen pre-trained representations when varying the number of samples per class for all three open-source diagnosis downstream tasks.

We can observe from the results achieved by the classifier on the PAD-UFES-20 and the HAM10000 dataset that (E) outperforms the other two models for all dataset sizes. For Fitzpatrick17k, we can see that there is not a clear winner among the three in the low data regimes. However, when then using all samples in the Fitzpatrick17k dataset method (E) is again able to outperform the other two. Further, we can see that for the Fitzpatrick17k dataset, the results achieved by a kNN classifier and a linear one are significantly better for all three methods. Additionally, we can see that for the PAD-UFES-20 and the HAM10000 dataset that the results are significantly lower compared to the linear evaluation, which shows the importance of evaluating both a linear and kNN classifier since their results can be dissimilar. However, although the performance of the two evaluations is different, the outcome is the same in both. The results from the Fitzpatrick17k and the HAM10000 show an expected behaviour of a rising curve when increasing the number of samples per class used for initialising the kNN classifier. Indicating that with more samples per class, the performance achieved by the classifier increases. However, for the PAD-UFES-20 dataset, this is not the case. For the last two steps, i.e. having 500 and all samples available per class, the performance decreases compared to the last. Such behaviour was unexpected since it was counterintuitive. One possible explanation for this would be that the embedding space is not separable, and images from different classes are projected near each other. Thus with more samples, such an embedding space would yield worse performance than when only having fewer data available. To conclude this experiment, the results show that the results achieved by (E) outperform, on average, the ones from the baseline over all three downstream tasks, indicating that its features are very competitive also in low data regimes.

4.5 Self-Supervised Pre-training and Fine-tuning Tips

This section uses the findings throughout the project, especially from the different experiments, to provide tips for pre-training and fine-tuning self-supervised learning methods for dermatology. It is important to note that this template is purely based on the experience from training various models in this project. Some recommendations are based on existing papers, and some are based on intuition. Thus this template might not work for everyone but should give a broad overview of the most important parts to spend some time optimising. The list below is sorted according to the components with the most impact on model performance.

Local and global crop size Both DINO and iBOT use a multi-crop data augmentation strategy for training, which means that they will crop smaller (local crops) and bigger (global crops) out of the input image. This augmentation strategy has shown to be one of the main driving factors in getting current SOTA SSL methods to work (Caron et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022). In the original paper of both DINO and iBOT they give detailed information about the used hyperparameters. However, when using the default values of the multi-crop augmentation strategy, no model converged to a suitable solution. Changing the local and global crop sizes resulted in major differences in the model performance. Thus by changing the multi-crop strategy, the models could then converge to a better solution. The strategy had to be adapted to make it work for dermatology images, i.e. the local crops had to be made smaller, and the global had to be made bigger.

SGD vs Adam vs AdamW vs LARS Using different optimisers can have a significant influence on the resulting SSL pre-trained model. During the experiments and due to non-converging models, different optimisers were used for pre-training. However, in this project, we have found that although changing the optimiser has a significant influence, sticking to the paper’s default is preferred, and one should rather spend time optimising different hyperparameters. One exception was that we could never get the LARS optimiser to work in this project, most likely due to not using large enough batch sizes. For fine-tuning SSL pre-trained models, different optimisers from the pre-training need to be used. However for fine-tuning the strategy is fairly simple, if the model is of type CNN use Adam, if of type ViT use SGD.

Projection head for fine-tuning Different papers have found that using not only the self-supervised pre-trained backbone but also parts or the entire projection head can yield an additional performance improvement (Caron et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022). In this project, we found this to be accurate, especially for the newer SSL methods such as DINO and iBOT and thus should always be examined.

Data augmentation during fine-tuning When using a pre-trained model with a ViT backbone during fine-tuning, we have found that they require much heavier regularisation and data augmentation than any CNN backbone. Recent papers have also found this to be true and thus provided recipes on how to successfully train ViTs (Steiner et al., 2021). In our experiments, we have found that the data augmentation technique has the most significant impact on the performance of the fine-tuned ViT. Thus in this project, we used two different techniques, a weaker one consisting of random rotation, flipping and minor colour distortion for the CNN backbones. For the ViTs we used the same weak augmentation as for the CNNs but changed the probabilities and the influence of the augmentations as well as added more aggressive techniques such as random erasing (Zhong et al., 2017b) and mixup (Zhang et al., 2017).

Monitoring SSL during pre-training Since the training objective during self-supervised pre-training is an artificially constructed signal out of unlabelled data, it is necessary to monitor the progress of the pre-training. Because the supervised signal is artificially constructed, having a lower validation loss does not always indicate a better model since the overall objective of the pre-training is yielding useful features. Therefore it is essential to monitor the model during this phase. The most straightforward way to monitor the models is to use them after a specific number of epochs and fine-tune it for multiple downstream tasks. Monitoring the fine-tuned performance during training indicates whether the pre-training yields meaningful features. Further qualitative evaluations such as visualising the embedding space can also help to find problems early on.

Learning rate schedulers for ViT During both the pre-training and fine-tuning in this project, no ViT was able to be trained without using a learning rate scheduler. Thus it is important to implement the same scheduler as proposed in the paper. If none is stated, one should first try a cosine scheduler since it has yielded strong performance in our experiments.

4.6 Summary of the Results

Five different self-supervised learning methods were pre-trained on a large dermatology dataset and evaluated on six different downstream tasks, namely ColorMe, BYOL, SimCLR, DINO and iBOT. Self-supervised learning methods were categorised by their used backbone architecture, i.e. CNN and ViT. Five different pre-training methods were evaluated using three different experiments, linear, fine-tuned and kNN evaluation and were compared to a supervised ImageNet pre-trained baseline. Across the different backbone architectures, a significant performance gap could be noticed across all experiments. In all three evaluations the pre-training methods using a ViT backbone outperformed the CNN backbone methods. In two of the two quantitative evaluations, the best performing method was iBOT, which is also currently considered the state of the art in self-supervised learning. Further iBOT pre-training was able to outperform the ImageNet baseline across almost all downstream tasks, although the performance differences were sometimes only minor. Astonishingly the best performing pre-training method, i.e. iBOT, uses as backbone a ViT-tiny, which features four times fewer parameters than the other evaluated backbones.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter provides an outlook regarding future work in section 5.1 and discusses the results of this project in section 5.2.

5.1 Outlook

Several aspects could potentially improve the current work. Additionally, further studies could be carried out based on the results of this project. Both the improvements and the further research ideas are listed below.

Ablation study In this project, we were able to show that using self-supervised pre-trained models can yield performance improvements for various downstream tasks compared to supervised pre-trained ImageNet weights. However, we can not conclude whether this performance improvement is due to the different architecture or caused by the pre-training since we only had supervised weights for CNN backbones available. By obtaining a supervised pre-trained ViT on ImageNet, the performance improvement could be traced back. Yet, we do not expect that such a ViT model is performing significantly better since the authors of the paper Dosovitskiy et al. (2020) mention that the amount of data available in ImageNet is not enough to outperform the CNN counterpart.

Experiments with larger ViT All ViTs in this project used a vanilla ViT-tiny architecture with a patch size of 16×16 . The tiny version of the transformer is mostly used for smoke tests because of its size and is often not evaluated on benchmark datasets. Thus, in future experiments, we want to examine how the performance of our pre-trained models' changes when using larger ViT models such as ViT-small or ViT-base. We expect that switching to these larger architectures would lead to a significant performance increase since these models then have more attention heads and layers that can be used to find minor features.

Improve segmentation model for ViT In the fine-tuning experiments, we saw that using pre-trained weights from iBOT can yield a substantial performance improvement across all classification tasks. However, for the segmentation tasks, this was not the case. For the ISIC 2018 Task 1 dataset, the pre-trained model outperformed the others, but for PPP segmentation, it did not. We hypothesise that the nature of the tasks causes this. For the ISIC task, the objective is to detect where the skin lesion is located, resulting in a coarse binary segmentation task. For the PPP segmentation, it is required to distinguish between skin, background and different types of pustules, which requires more fine-grained localisation information. Recent literature has proposed many different decoder architectures for ViTs, which should enable the model to reconstruct fine-grained spatial information using skip-connections and attentions in the decoder part. Thus, by implementing more recent decoders for the ViT, we expect to improve the resulting fine-tuned performance.

Few-shot classification using pre-trained models In the experiments, we implemented one of the simplest few-shot classification schemas, k -nearest neighbour (kNN), to examine how the pre-trained models perform in low data and few-shot regimes. The results from this evaluation seemed promising. Thus, in future experiments, we want to evaluate how and if the performance

changes when using more recent few-shot learning strategies. Having few-shot models in the medical domain would be especially beneficial since rare diseases and out-of-distribution samples are a minority but, in some cases, available. Thus, this would enable better recognition of such diseases.

Examine domain adaption performance One of the biggest problems in dermatology is domain adaption since the training data, and the final application data are likely to be different and will often also change over time. Thus, having models that can adapt to unseen domains is sometimes even a requirement. We hypothesise that using models pre-trained on dermatology data can lead to better generalisation to unseen domains than those pre-trained on natural image datasets. In future experiments, we want to examine if this is true and how different the domains can be to still perform reasonably.

5.2 Conclusion

This project aimed to apply self-supervised pre-training to dermatology images and to examine the differences between using supervised pre-trained models from natural image datasets such as ImageNet. For pre-training, the university hospital of Basel has kindly provided us with a dataset of approximately 250'000 dermatology images. To evaluate the differences between supervised and self-supervised pre-training, we used six different downstream tasks, four of which originated from open-source benchmark datasets, and two were private tasks from the university hospital. Two of the six downstream tasks were segmentation tasks, and the other four were classification tasks. Five different self-supervised learning algorithms were evaluated in this project, namely ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO and iBOT. All five models were pre-trained on the same dataset from the university hospital. After training, the models were first qualitatively evaluated by examining the resulting embedding space for specific downstream tasks and plotting the nearest neighbours from a given anchor image. Afterwards, they were evaluated using three different methods, linear (see 4.2), fine-tuned (see 4.3) and kNN performance (see 4.4).

During the experiments, multiple noteworthy findings were made. For example, the qualitative evaluation showed that some models were more likely to produce embedding spaces incorporating skin colour than others, resulting in nearest neighbours for some models being of the same skin type as the anchor image. Further, the linear evaluation showed that only models using a ViT backbone were able to outperform the supervised pre-trained model. However also for the pre-trained ViT models only iBOT outperformed ImageNet across all tasks. The fine-tuning performance on the open-source tasks then showed a similar image as the linear evaluation, where only iBOT was able to outperform ImageNet across all tasks for both classification and segmentation. For the fine-tuned performance on the private tasks, iBOT was still the best performing one but could only outperform the ImageNet counterpart on the classification task and not on the segmentation.

To conclude, this project showed that using self-supervised pre-training can yield a significant performance difference compared to supervised pre-trained ImageNet models. The best performing SSL pre-training was iBOT since it outperformed all of the other pre-trainings and ImageNet pre-training in almost all evaluations. However, there is still some uncertainty if the performance difference by iBOT is caused by the difference in architecture or the pre-training method. Thus in future experiments, we plan ablation experiments to determine if the performance gain is really due to the pre-training task or influenced by the different architecture.

Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Source Code

The following section should give a brief overview of the implemented code. Furthermore, it should also show how the experiments can be repeated and verified.

A.1.1 Makefile

Every experiment in this project was scripted to ensure reproducibility. For this purpose, a Makefile was written that can be used to run experiments, test the code and for debugging. Figure A.1 shows all possible Make targets in the project. Additionally, all experiments used “.yaml” files for specifying the hyperparameters, which can also be found in the source code and the directory of the trained models.

```
TARGETS

INFO set the ENV variable to run the targets using 'prod' or 'dev' configuration, default is 'prod'

Docker:

run_bash runs on interactive bash inside the docker image
run_gpu_bash runs on interactive bash inside the docker image with a GPU

Eval:

eval_imagenet evaluates a pretrained ImageNet ResNet on downstream
eval_simclr evaluates SimCLR on downstream
eval_byol evaluates BYOL on downstream
eval_dino evaluates DINO on downstream
eval_ibot evaluates IBOT on downstream
eval_colorme evaluates ColorMe on downstream

SSH:

push_ssh pushes all the directories along with the files to a remote SSH server
pull_ssh pulls directories from a remote SSH server

Training:

train_simclr trains SimCLR
train_byol trains BYOL
train_colorme trains ColorMe
train_dino trains DINO
train_ibot trains IBOT

Training-DGX:

train_simclr_docker trains SimCLR for Multi GPU training in Docker Container
train_byol_docker trains BYOL for Multi GPU training in Docker Container
train_colorme_docker trains ColorMe for Multi GPU training in Docker Container
train_dino_docker trains DINO for Multi GPU training in Docker Container
train_ibot_docker trains IBOT for Multi GPU training in Docker Container

Usage:

help show this help

Utils:

init initializes the project and pulls all the necessary data
update_data_ref updates the reference to the submodule to its latest commit
clean cleans the project
test runs all tests in the project (unit and integration tests)
```

Figure A.1: Output of running `make help` in the project directory, i.e. list of all Make targets

A.2 Pre-training Hyperparameters

This section details the hyperparameters used to pre-training the self-supervised models from the experiment chapter 4.

A.2.1 ColorMe

This subsection lists all the hyperparameters used to train ColorMe and the parameters tested to find a model that converges to a suitable solution.

Hyperparameter	Value	Tested Values
batch_size	200	[128, 200]
epochs	100	
optim	sgd	[adam, sgd]
lr	0.001	[0.01, 0.001, 0.001, 0.003]
min_lr	1e-6	
weight_decay	1e-6	
weight_decay_end	0.4	
warmup_epochs	10	
clip_grad	3.0	
use_lr_scheduler	False	[True, False]
use_wd_scheduler	False	[True, False]
seed	42	
model/emb_dim	2048	
model/out_dim	256	
model/base_model	resnet50	
model/model_type	UNET	
dataset/wrapper/target_shape	(224,224,3)	
loss/weight_mse	10.0	[1.0, 2.0, 5.0, 10.0]
loss/weight_kld	1.0	

Table A.1: List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for ColorMe

A.2.2 SimCLR

This subsection lists all the hyperparameters used to train SimCLR and the parameters tested to find a model that converges to a suitable solution.

Hyperparameter	Value	Tested Values
batch_size	640	[512, 600, 640]
epochs	100	
optim	adam	[adam, lars]
lr	0.00003	[0.00003, 0.001, 0.0001, 0.0003]
min_lr	1e-6	
weight_decay	1e-6	
weight_decay_end	0.4	
warmup_epochs	10	
clip_grad	3.0	
use_lr_scheduler	True	
use_wd_scheduler	True	
seed	42	
model/emb_dim	2048	
model/out_dim	128	
model/base_model	resnet50	
model/model_type	CNN	
dataset/augmentations/target_size	224	
dataset/augmentations/gaussian_kernel	23	
dataset/augmentations/scaling	1	
loss/temperature	0.5	
loss/use_cosine_similarity	True	

Table A.2: List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for SimCLR

A.2.3 BYOL

This subsection lists all the hyperparameters used to train BYOL and the parameters tested to find a model that converges to a suitable solution.

Hyperparameter	Value	Tested Values
batch_size	60	[32, 50, 60]
epochs	100	
optim	adam	[sgd, adam]
lr	0.003	[0.0001, 0.0003, 0.001, 0.003]
min_lr	1e-6	
weight_decay	1.5e-5	[1e-5, 1.5e-5, 1e-6]
warmup_epochs	10	
momentum_base	0.996	
clip_grad	3.0	
use_lr_scheduler	True	
use_wd_scheduler	False	
seed	42	
model/emb_dim	2048	
model/out_dim	256	
model/base_model	resnet50	
model/model_type	CNN	
model/byol/projection_hidden_size	4096	
model/byol/projection_size	256	
model/byol/hidden_layer	-2	
model/byol/use_momentum	True	
dataset/augmentations/target_size	224	
dataset/augmentations/gaussian_kernel	23	
dataset/augmentations/scaling	0.5	
dataset/augmentations/two_augmentations	True	
loss/temperature	0.5	
loss/use_cosine_similarity	True	

Table A.3: List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for BYOL

A.2.4 DINO

This subsection lists all the hyperparameters used to train DINO and the parameters tested to find a model that converges to a suitable solution.

Hyperparameter	Value	Tested Values
batch_size	260	[128, 200, 260]
epochs	100	
optim	adamw	
lr	0.0005	[0.05, 0.005, 0.0005]
min_lr	1e-6	[5e-4, 1e-6]
weight_decay	0.04	
weight_decay_end	0.4	
warmup_epochs	10	
momentum_teacher	0.9995	[0.9995, 0.996]
clip_grad	3.0	[None, 3.0]
use_lr_scheduler	True	
use_wd_scheduler	True	
seed	42	
model/out_dim	4096	
model/emb_dim	192	
model/base_model	vit_tiny	
model/model_type	VIT	
model/use_bn_in_head	False	
model/norm_last_layer	True	
model/student/patch_size	16	
model/student/drop_path_rate	0.1	
model/teacher/drop_path_rate	0.1	
model/eval/n_last_blocks	4	
model/eval/avgpool_patchtokens	False	
dataset/augmentations/global_crops_scale	(0.7, 1.)	[(0.14, 1.), (0.4, 1.), (0.7, 1.)]
dataset/augmentations/local_crops_scale	(0.05, 0.4)	[(0.05, 0.4), (0.05, 0.7)]
dataset/augmentations/global_crops_number	2	
dataset/augmentations/local_crops_number	12	[8, 10, 12]
loss/warmup_teacher_temp	0.04	
loss/teacher_temp	0.04	
loss/warmup_teacher_temp_epochs	30	
optimiser/freeze_last_layer	1	[1, 2]

Table A.4: List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for DINO

A.2.5 iBOT

This subsection lists all the hyperparameters used to train iBOT and the parameters tested to find a model that converges to a suitable solution.

Hyperparameter	Value	Tested Values
batch_size	224	[128, 160, 200, 224]
epochs	100	
optim	adamw	
lr	0.005	[0.05, 0.005, 0.0005]
min_lr	5e-4	[5e-4, 1e-6]
weight_decay	0.04	
weight_decay_end	0.4	
warmup_epochs	10	
momentum_teacher	0.996	[0.9995, 0.996]
clip_grad	3.0	[None, 3.0]
use_lr_scheduler	True	
use_wd_scheduler	True	
seed	42	
model/out_dim	4096	
model/emb_dim	192	
model/patch_out_dim	4096	
model/base_model	vit_tiny	
model/model_type	VIT	
model/use_bn_in_head	False	
model/norm_last_layer	True	[True, False]
model/shared_head	True	[True, False]
model/shared_head_teacher	True	[True, False]
model/student/patch_size	16	
model/student/drop_path_rate	0.1	
model/student/return_all_tokens	True	
model/student/masked_lm_modeling	True	
model/teacher/patch_size	16	
model/teacher/drop_path_rate	0.1	
model/teacher/return_all_tokens	True	
model/eval/n_last_blocks	4	
model/eval/avgpool_patchtokens	False	
dataset/augmentations/global_crops_scale	(0.7, 1.)	[(0.14, 1.), (0.4, 1.), (0.7, 1.)]
dataset/augmentations/local_crops_scale	(0.05, 0.4)	[(0.05, 0.4), (0.05, 0.7)]
dataset/augmentations/global_crops_number	2	
dataset/augmentations/local_crops_number	12	[8, 10, 12]
dataset/MIM/pred_ratio	0.3	
dataset/MIM/pred_ratio_var	0.0	
dataset/MIM/pred_aspect_ratio	(0.3, 1/0.3)	
dataset/MIM/pred_shape	block	
dataset/MIM/pred_start_epoch	0	
loss/warmup_teacher_temp	0.04	
loss/teacher_temp	0.04	
loss/warmup_teacher_patch_temp	0.04	
loss/teacher_patch_temp	0.07	
loss/warmup_teacher_temp_epochs	30	
loss/lambda1	1.00	
loss/lambda2	1.00	
optimiser/freeze_last_layer	1	[1, 2]

Table A.5: List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for iBOT

A.3 Pre-training Data Augmentation

This section details the implemented data augmentation method for the four SSL methods that use and depend on augmentation.

A.3.1 SimCLR

This subsection shows the data augmentation strategy implemented and used to train SimCLR.

Algorithm 9 Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in SimCLR which creates two random views given an input image.

Input: *img*: RGB image of various size

Output: *img_aug_1*: augmented view of size 224×224 , *img_aug_2*: augmented view of size 224×224

```
def data_aug(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.5)
    return img_aug
def simclr(img):
    img_aug_1 = data_aug(img)
    img_aug_2 = data_aug(img)
    return img_aug_1, img_aug_2
```

A.3.2 BYOL

This subsection shows the data augmentation strategy implemented and used to train BYOL.

Algorithm 10 Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in BYOL which creates two random views given an input image.

Input: *img*: RGB image of various size

Output: *img_aug_1*: augmented view of size 224×224 , *img_aug_2*: augmented view of size 224×224

```
def data_aug_1(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.5)
    return img_aug
def data_aug_2(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.1)
    img_aug = solarisation(img_aug, p=0.2)
    return img_aug
def byol(img):
    img_aug_1 = data_aug_1(img)
    img_aug_2 = data_aug_2(img)
    return img_aug_1, img_aug_2
```

A.3.3 DINO

This subsection shows the data augmentation strategy implemented and used to train DINO.

Algorithm 11 Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in DINO which creates global and local crops given an input image.

Input: *img*: RGB image of various size, n_l : number of local crops

Output: *crops*: list of two global and n_l local crops

```
def global_aug_1(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=1.0)
    return img_aug
def global_aug_2(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.1)
    img_aug = solarisation(img_aug, p=0.2)
    return img_aug
def local_aug_2(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=96)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.5)
    return img_aug
def dino_aug(img,  $n_l$ ):
    crops = []
    crops.append(global_aug_1(img))
    crops.append(global_aug_2(img))
    for  $n_l$ :
        | crops.append(local_aug(img))
    return crops
```

A.3.4 iBOT

This subsection shows the data augmentation strategy implemented and used to train iBOT.

Algorithm 12 Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in iBOT which creates global and local crops given an input image.

Input: *img*: RGB image of various size, n_g : number of global crops, n_l : number of local crops

Output: *crops*: list of n_g global and n_l local crops

```

def global_aug_1(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=1.0)
    return img_aug
def global_aug_2(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=224)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.1)
    img_aug = solarisation(img_aug, p=0.2)
    return img_aug
def local_aug_2(img):
    img_aug = resized_crop(img, size=96)
    img_aug = horizontal_flip(img_aug, p=0.5)
    img_aug = color_jitter(img_aug, p=0.8)
    img_aug = greyscale(img_aug, p=0.2)
    img_aug = gaussian_blur(img_aug, sigma=(0.1, 2), p=0.5)
    return img_aug
def ibot_aug(img,  $n_l$ ):
    crops = []
    crops.append(global_aug_1(img))
    for  $n_g - 1$ :
        | crops.append(global_aug_2(img))
    for  $n_l$ :
        | crops.append(local_aug(img))
    return crops

```

A.4 Fine-tuning Hyperparameter Grid

This section describes the hyperparameter grid used to perform a parameter sweep for the respective downstream tasks, i.e. used for fine-tuning.

A.4.1 Classification

Hyperparameter	Grid
batch size	[64, 128, 256]
color jitter	[0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.05]
dropout	[0.2, 0.3, 0.5]
image size	[224, 260]
label smoothing	[0.2, 0.1, 0.01]
large head	[True, False]
loss function	[CE, NLL]
learning rate	[0.01, 0.03, 0.001, 0.003, 0.0001]
n.o. head layers	[0, 1, 2, 3]
optimiser	[ADAM, SGD]
random rotation	[20, 90, 180]
use mixup	[True, False]
use random erasing	[True, False]

Table A.6: List of the parameter grid used for hyperparameter-optimisation for fine-tuning the classification tasks.

A.4.2 Segmentation

Hyperparameter	Grid
batch size	[64, 128, 256]
image size	[224, 512]
loss function	[dice, tversky, focal]
learning rate	[0.01, 0.03, 0.001, 0.003, 0.0001]
optimiser	[ADAM, SGD]

Table A.7: List of the parameter grid used for hyperparameter-optimisation for fine-tuning the segmentation tasks.

A.5 Published Paper at the SDAIH Workshop of the ECAI Conference

The accepted paper, written during this project and submitted to the SDAIH workshop at the ECAI conference, is attached on the following pages. The paper will be published as proceedings to SciTePress.

Towards Reducing The Need For Annotations In Digital Dermatology With Self-Supervised Learning

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Abstract: Training supervised models requires large amounts of labeled data, whose creation is often expensive and time-consuming, especially in the medical domain. The standard practice to mitigate the lack of annotated clinical images is to use transfer learning and fine-tune pre-trained ImageNet weights on a downstream task. While this approach achieves satisfactory performance, it still requires a sufficiently large dataset to adjust the global features for a specific task. We report on an ongoing investigation to determine whether self-supervised learning methods applied to unlabelled domain-specific images can provide better representations for digital dermatology compared to ImageNet. We consider ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO, and iBOT, and present preliminary results on the evaluation of pre-trained initialization for three different medical tasks with mixed imaging modalities. Our intermediate findings indicate a benefit in using features learned by iBOT on dermatology datasets compared to conventional transfer learning from ImageNet classification.

Keywords: self-supervised learning; pre-training; transfer learning; dermatology; medical imaging

1. Introduction

Current artificial intelligence applications to medical imaging often rely on **Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs)** trained in a supervised way. These models have shown remarkable performance across many tasks due to their ability to deal with raw image data [1]. **CNNs** typically require vast amounts of annotated data to achieve high levels of performance and robustness. However, medical images can be hard to obtain: The acquisition process needs to consider strict regulations, collection biases should be appropriately mitigated [2], and examples of rare conditions are challenging to find.

Dermatology is a field of medicine where image analysis can have a significant impact since many pathologies are visible with a naked eye and can easily be photographed. Two main types of images are usually considered: dermoscopy pictures taken with a dedicated device called “dermatoscope”, which is almost in direct contact with the skin and offers magnification, and ordinary clinical images, which are instead collected with cameras that are not specifically designed for dermatology.

Although a diagnosis is usually reported in patient files, one typically needs to recruit and train several dermatologists to do a tedious labeling job if more detailed information is required. Moreover, for several medical conditions, it is hard to get experts to agree on a common answer [3]. This explains why the most popular general-purpose image dataset, ImageNet [4], has 200 times more pictures than the biggest public dermoscopy dataset and 2000 times more than the largest public clinical image collection¹.

Transfer learning can leverage knowledge from a source task with plenty of data to perform a target task where data is limited. The most common approach to transfer learning

Citation: Gröger, F.; Gottfrois, P.; Amruthalingam, L.; Gonzalez-Jimenez A.; Lionetti S.; Navarini N.; Pouly M. Towards reducing the need for annotations in digital dermatology with self-supervised learning. *Comput. Sci. Math. Forum* **2022**, *1*, 0. <https://doi.org/>

Published:

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¹ <https://www.isic-archive.com/>, accessed on 20.05.2022

is pre-training large models such as [residual neural network \(ResNet\)](#) on huge labeled image datasets. Models pre-trained on ImageNet are also widely used in the medical domain, which is controversial since features extracted from natural images, may not be ideal representations in some medical contexts [5].

[Self-supervised learning \(SSL\)](#) is a hybrid approach that strives to combine supervised and unsupervised learning and is also often used through pre-training followed by adaptation [6]. It aims at learning semantically useful features by creating a supervised objective from a pool of unlabelled data without the need for human annotation. This objective is often called the *pretext task*. Learnt features can then be used in *downstream tasks* where annotated data is scarce. In recent years, [SSL](#) became popular also in the medical domain as large volumes of unlabelled data are easier to obtain than their annotated counterparts. Several works have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach for detection and classification [7], for detection and localization [8], and for segmentation [9].

In this paper, we report intermediate results from an ongoing investigation on using [SSL](#) to mitigate the need for annotated samples in dermatology. We train several prominent [SSL](#) algorithms on a mixed dataset of 250'000 skin images, both from dermoscopy and clinical pictures. We then research the impact of using these representations as a starting point for different medical imaging tasks in dermatology.

2. Self-supervised Learning Techniques

In this section, we briefly review the different [SSL](#) techniques considered in this work.

2.1. ColorMe

[ColorMe](#) [10] was specifically designed for applications in the medical domain and embeds inductive bias in its two pretext tasks. It uses an encoder to map the green channel of an image to a vector space. This is followed both by a decoder, which learns to reconstruct the pixel values of the red and blue channels and by a fully-connected layer, which learns to predict the overall color distribution of the red and blue channels.

2.2. SimCLR

[A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations \(SimCLR\)](#) [11] proposes to obtain different views of the same image with heavy data augmentation, called positive samples, and minimize the distance between their representations. At the same time, the distance between views of different images in the same batch, the negative samples, is maximized. The encoder is typically a [ResNet](#) architecture followed by a projection head to be discarded after training.

2.3. BYOL

[Bootstrap your own latent \(BYOL\)](#) [12] compares embeddings of image views obtained from two networks, removing the need for negative samples. The first network is termed *online* and consists of an encoder, a projection head, and a prediction head. The second network is known as *target*, has the same architecture as the online network except for the prediction head, and its weights are an exponential moving average of the online network weights. The training objective is to match the online network's output with the target network's output using mean squared error.

2.4. DINO

[Self-distillation with no labels \(DINO\)](#) [13] uses a similar principle to [BYOL](#), but it passes transformations of an image into two separate encoders, respectively the student and the teacher networks. Unlike previous [SSL](#) approaches the encoder is a [vision transformer \(ViT\)](#) [14]. The loss compares the probability outputs of both networks using cross-entropy. Only the weights of the student are updated via backpropagation, while the parameters of the teacher are an exponential moving average of the student.

2.5. *iBOT*

Image BERT pretraining with online tokenizer (*iBOT*) [15] exploits inherent properties of ViTs to learn representations capturing local and global information. Similarly to *DINO*, *iBOT* uses a student network that is trained and a teacher network which is an exponential moving average. Its loss function is the sum of two cross-entropies. The first one compares the output of the two networks when they are given different views of the same image. And the second one, when the two networks are both passed the same view, but some patches are masked for the student, matches the outputs corresponding to those patches.

3. Experimental Setup

3.1. Pretraining Data

The training data includes both dermoscopy and clinical images, with the hypothesis that there are common patterns in skin pictures taken at different magnifications. In total, we use 242'292 images from both public and private datasets as listed below.

- *derm7pt* [16], featuring 2'020 dermoscopy and clinical images of various skin pigmentation lesions.
- *ISIC²*, which consists of 107'208 dermoscopy images with a wide spectrum of pigmented skin lesions mostly on low-pigmentation skin. We exclude pictures overlapping with *HAM10000* [17] as these are used in a downstream task.
- *MED-NODE* [18], which includes 170 clinical images of pigmented skin lesions.
- *SD-260* [19], containing 12'583 clinical images of 260 different skin conditions.
- *Ph2* [20], containing 453 dermoscopy images of pigmented skin lesions.
- A private dataset of 119'858 clinical images, reflecting the data distribution encountered in a Swiss hospital. Pictures were taken using diverse reflex cameras by a trained photographer, were anonymized, and used with approval (EKNZ-2018-01074) from an ethical committee according to Swiss regulations.

3.2. Downstream tasks

To evaluate the performance of the pre-training methods, we use three different downstream tasks, which were not present in the pre-training data.

- *Fitzpatrick17k* [2] is a public benchmark dataset, which contains 16'577 clinical images with skin condition annotations and skin type labels based on the Fitzpatrick scoring system. The dataset contains labels with different granularity. This study used the coarsest level, which splits skin conditions into three main categories.
- *PAD-UFES-20* [21] is a public benchmark dataset composed of clinical images collected from smartphone devices and patient metadata. The dataset consists of 1'373 patients, 1'641 skin lesions, and 2'298 images for six different diagnoses: three skin diseases and three skin cancers.
- *HAM10000* [17] is a public benchmark dataset consisting of 10'015 dermoscopic images gathered from different cohorts. The collected cases include a representative sample of seven diagnostic categories of pigmented lesions.

3.3. Architectures

The SSL algorithms considered can be split into two groups based on the backbone architecture they work with, which can be a CNN or a ViT. To ensure a fair comparison, at least within the same group, we used the very same model when possible. To further promote the correspondence between the two groups, we selected architectures that perform similarly on ImageNet. For the CNN-based models we chose *ResNet-50*, and for the ViT-based ones a tiny vision transformer [14] with patch size of 16×16 . The number of trainable parameters is therefore roughly 23 Mio. for *ResNet-50* and 5.4 Mio. for *ViT-tiny*.

² <https://www.isic-archive.com/>, accessed on 20.05.2022

Table 1. Hyperparameters of the different [self-supervised learning](#) techniques.

Algorithm	Backbone	# Params	Optimizer	Batch size	Lr.	Scheduler
ColorMe	ResNet50	23 Mio.	SGD	50	1×10^{-3}	-
SimCLR	ResNet50	23 Mio.	Adam	160	3×10^{-5}	cosine
BYOL	ResNet50	23 Mio.	Adam	150	3×10^{-3}	cosine
DINO	ViT-tiny	5.4 Mio.	AdamW	56	5×10^{-4}	cosine
iBOT	ViT-tiny	5.4 Mio.	AdamW	56	5×10^{-4}	cosine

Table 2. Macro-averaged F1 scores of various models and a baseline on the hold-out test set of the three open-source dermatology downstream tasks. After adding a linear layer, both freezing and fine-tuning the backbone are considered.

Evaluation	Pre-training	Fitzpatrick17k	PAD-UFES-20	HAM10000
Linear Eval.	Stratified sampling	33.4 %	18.0 %	14.0 %
	ImageNet	51.0 %	49.7 %	54.1 %
	ColorMe	44.8 %	42.2 %	47.0 %
	SimCLR	37.0 %	32.7 %	28.2 %
	BYOL	48.1 %	34.4 %	44.4 %
	DINO	46.7 %	44.2 %	57.2 %
Fine-tuned	iBOT	53.0 %	58.2 %	72.0 %
	ImageNet	72.1 %	61.5 %	79.0 %
	ColorMe	71.0 %	61.7 %	73.1 %
	iBOT	73.9 %	62.3 %	82.0 %

3.4. Hyperparameters

Table 1 gives some details about the hyperparameters for pre-training. All images are resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized. Further, the models are trained until the validation loss does not improve consecutively over five epochs. A full scan of hyperparameter space is not performed as this exceeds the scope of this paper and our available computational resources. However, we ensure that all models converge to a suitable solution by manually choosing an appropriate optimizer and tuning the learning rate. We use the same data augmentation policies described in the original paper introducing each pretext task.

3.5. Evaluation

To compare the representations learned by different pre-training strategies, we test them in two ways: using linear evaluation on frozen embeddings and fine-tuning the whole model. Both experiments are performed on all downstream tasks. For models using a ResNet backbone, we add the linear layer after the last average pooling layer. For ViT-based models, we follow the [13] and add a linear layer after the concatenation of the class token to the last four blocks in the model. In the fine-tuning experiment, the backbone and the linear classification head are trained together.

Finally, to better understand the utility of self-supervised pre-training in different low-data regimes, we also train a simple *k*-nearest neighbor (kNN) classifier that acts as a few-shot learner for the downstream tasks. This classifier learns from a random subset of the downstream task's labeled data and is evaluated on the same hold-out test set as the linear evaluation and the fine-tuning.

4. Results

Scores that probe the ability of self-supervised pre-trained features to generalize to the three downstream tasks are reported in table 2. The upper half shows the performance of frozen pre-trained embeddings upon linear evaluation. All models show better results compared to the random stratified sampling baseline. However, we also observe that the

Figure 1. Results of a **kNN** classifier on pre-trained representations when varying the number of samples per class for all three downstream tasks.

results of ColorMe, SimCLR and BYOL are worse than the performance achieved by using ImageNet features. This indicates that models with a CNN backbone do not profit from domain-specific pre-training in our setting and are better off using general features such as the ones from ImageNet. A possible explanation for this is that such models have a strong inductive bias which benefits more from initialization using general pre-trained weights [5]. Features from a ViT backbone yield less uniform patterns in comparison with ImageNet. DINO is only able to outperform the general features in one of three tasks and only by 3%. On the other hand, the results clearly show that iBOT performs well across all tasks and yields an improvement over ImageNet initialization by 2%, 9.5%, and 17.9%, respectively.

The lower half of table 2 summarizes the performance upon fine-tuning the pre-trained features. Here we only report results for the reference ImageNet model and the two models which obtained the highest average scores in the CNN and ViT classes of SSL approaches, i.e. ColorMe and iBOT. Similar to the results from the linear evaluation, we observe that using iBOT as initialization yields the best performance for all downstream tasks. Furthermore, we notice that the gap between ColorMe and iBOT is smaller than using linear evaluation, indicating that with enough training data and trainable parameters, similar features can be learned. Comparing the performance in the linear and fine-tuned evaluation, we can also see that the improvement for iBOT on PAD-UFES-20 and HAM10000 is noticeably smaller with respect to other methods. This suggests that the inherent structure of the dataset labels was already learned in the pre-training phase, and only minor adaptations to the existing features could be done.

Finally, figure 1 shows the results of adding a kNN classifier to the pre-trained ColorMe, iBOT and ImageNet features upon changing the training dataset size. The results achieved by iBOT outperform, on average, the ones from ImageNet over all three downstream tasks, indicating that its features are very competitive also in low data regimes.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we set out to investigate whether features from domain-specific self-supervised pre-training yield a benefit over general-purpose ones such as ImageNet weights, which are currently the *de facto* standard in the medical domain. The results achieved so far indicate that there might be an advantage in SSL initialization, especially when using iBOT. However, we currently cannot conclude whether this benefit can be traced back to the pre-training strategy or the difference in model architecture. An indication in favor of the former is that DINO, which is also based on ViTs, did not outperform ImageNet initialization. In the future, we plan ablation experiments to determine if the performance gain is really due to the pre-training task or influenced by the different architecture.

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List of Abbreviations

- Adam** adaptive moment estimation. 9, 10, 37, 49
- AdamW** adaptive moment estimation with weight decay. 10, 37, 49
- ANN** artificial neural network. 3
- BYOL** bootstrap your own latent. 25, 26, 37, 41–44, 50, 52, 59, 70, 72, 73
- CNN** convolutional neural network. 1, 14–17, 20, 21, 23, 26, 36–39, 45–47, 49–51
- DINO** self-distillation with no labels. 26, 27, 37, 41–44, 49, 50, 52, 60, 70, 72
- GD** gradient descent. 8, 9
- GRU** gated recurrent unit. 18
- iBOT** image BERT pretraining with online tokenizer. II, 27, 28, 37, 41–44, 49–52, 61, 70, 72
- IoU** intersection over union. 8, 40, 73
- KLD** Kullback-Leibler divergence. 7, 29, 73
- kNN** k -nearest neighbour. II, 21, 41, 48, 50–52, 70, 73
- LSTM** long short-term memory. 18
- MLP** multi-layer perceptron. 4, 14, 20, 24
- MSE** mean squared error. 7, 25, 29, 73
- NLP** natural language processing. 18
- NN** neural network. 3–6, 8, 12, 21
- NT-XEnt** normalized temperature-scaled cross entropy. 24, 73
- PPP** palmoplantar pustular psoriasis. II, 32, 33, 46, 47, 51
- ReLU** rectified linear unit. 6, 8, 16, 24, 39
- ResNet** residual neural network. 1, 17, 24, 36, 39, 41, 45, 47
- RMSProp** root mean square propagation. 9
- RNN** recurrent neural network. 11, 18, 19
- SGD** stochastic gradient descent. 8, 9, 37, 45, 49
- SimCLR** a simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations. 24, 25, 37, 41–44, 50, 52, 59, 70, 72
- SOTA** state of the art. 12, 27, 41, 49, 50
- SSL** self-supervised learning. II, 1, 3, 22, 27, 29, 31, 34, 36–38, 41–46, 48–50, 52, 59, 70, 71
- tanh** hyperbolic tangent. 6, 16, 70
- ViT** vision transformer. 20, 26, 27, 36–39, 41, 45–47, 49–52

List of Figures

2.1	Visualisation of a perceptron	3
2.2	Visualisation of a multilevel perceptron	4
2.3	The sigmoid activation function	5
2.4	The tanh activation function	6
2.5	The ReLU activation function	7
2.6	Illustration of the gradient clipping problem	12
2.7	Visualisation of a convolutional operation	14
2.8	Illustration of the dense connectivity of feed-forward networks	15
2.9	Illustration of the sparse connectivity of convolutional networks	15
2.10	Vizualisation of the max- and average-pooling operation	16
2.11	ResNet visualisations	17
2.12	Visualisation of the Transformer architecture	19
2.13	Illustration of the ViT model	20
2.14	Overview of the SimCLR method	24
2.15	Overview of the BYOL method	26
2.16	Visualisation of the multi-crop data augmentation strategy	27
2.17	Overview of the DINO method	27
2.18	Overview of the iBOT method	28
2.19	Overview of the ColorMe method	29
2.20	Examples of images found in dermatology	30
3.1	Samples of the four different open-source downstream tasks.	33
3.2	Data augmentations applied to the images in the downstream tasks	35
3.3	Illustration of the U-Net model	38
3.4	Illustration of the TransUNet model	39
4.1	Two-dimensional visualisation of the HAM10000 embedding space for all SSL methods .	42
4.2	Two-dimensional visualisation of the Fitzpatrick17k embedding space for all SSL methods	43
4.3	Nearest neighbours of the different SSL methods from the Fitzpatrick17k dataset.	44
4.4	Results of a kNN classifier on frozen pre-trained representations when varying the number of samples per class for all three open-source diagnosis downstream tasks.	48
A.1	Output of running <code>make help</code> in the project directory, i.e. list of all Make targets	53

List of Tables

3.1	List of the different downstream tasks.	32
3.2	List of backbones used with the different self-supervised learning methods along with the respective total number of parameters.	38
4.1	Macro-averaged F1 scores of various models and a baseline on the hold-out test set of the three open-source dermatology diagnosis downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the frozen backbone to evaluate linear performance of the initialisation strategies.	45
4.2	Macro-averaged F1 and mIoU scores of two self-supervised models and a baseline reported on the hold-out test set of the four open-source downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the trainable backbone to evaluate the fine-tuned performance of the initialisation strategies.	46
4.3	Macro-averaged F1 and mIoU scores of two self-supervised models and a baseline reported on the hold-out test set of the two private downstream tasks. A linear layer was added to the trainable backbone to evaluate the fine-tuned performance of the initialisation strategies.	47
A.1	List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for ColorMe	54
A.2	List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for SimCLR	55
A.3	List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for BYOL	56
A.4	List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for DINO	57
A.5	List of the hyperparameters along with the tested values for iBOT	58
A.6	List of the parameter grid used for hyperparameter-optimisation for fine-tuning the classification tasks.	62
A.7	List of the parameter grid used for hyperparameter-optimisation for fine-tuning the segmentation tasks.	62

List of Algorithms

1	Gradient descent algorithm	8
2	Momentum algorithm	9
3	RMSProp algorithm	9
4	Adam algorithm	9
5	AdamW algorithm	10
6	Batch normalisation	11
7	Layer normalisation	11
8	Classification head, given the pre-trained encoder (<code>enc</code>) and image (<code>img</code>).	38
9	Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in SimCLR which creates two random views given an input image.	59
10	Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in BYOL which creates two random views given an input image.	59
11	Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in DINO which creates global and local crops given an input image.	60
12	Pseudocode of the image data augmentation implemented in iBOT which creates global and local crops given an input image.	61

List of Equations

2.0	Calculates the output of single layer neural network	4
2.1	Gradient of cost function with respect to the weights	5
2.2	Heaviside function	5
2.3	Sigmoid function	5
2.4	Derivative of the sigmoid function	5
2.5	Softmax function	6
2.6	Tangens hyperbolicus function	6
2.7	Derivative of the tangens hyperbolicus function	6
2.8	Rectified linear unit function	6
2.9	Derivative of the rectified linear unit function	6
2.10	Mean squared error cost function	7
2.11	Cross-entropy cost function	7
2.12	Binary cross-entropy cost function	7
2.13	Kullback-Leibler divergence cost function	7
2.14	Dice cost function	8
2.15	Weight normalisation	11
2.16	Gradient clipping by norm	12
2.19	Attention scores calculations	18
2.20	Attention weights calculation	18
2.21	Context vector calculation	18
2.22	k -nearest neighbour (kNN) prediction	21
2.23	Mahalanobis distance	21
2.24	Cosine distance	21
2.25	Definition of the original contrastive loss function	23
2.26	Triplet loss constraint	23
2.27	Triplet loss function	23
2.28	NT-XEnt loss	24
2.29	Cosine similarity	25
2.30	Update rule of the target network ξ based on an exponential moving average of the online network θ	25
2.31	BYOL MSE loss function	25
2.32	BYOL loss function	25
3.0	Accuracy	40
3.1	Recall	40
3.2	Precision	40
3.3	F_1 score	40
3.4	IoU score	40

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